

SPACE ROCKS:
a series of papers on
METEORITES AND ASTEROIDS

by
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Of all investments into the future, the conquest of space demands the greatest efforts and the longest-term commitment, but it also offers the greatest reward: none less than a universe.

— *Daniel Christlein*

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Abstract

The subject of this work is the compositions of asteroids and meteorites. Studies of the composition of small Solar System bodies are fundamental to theories of planet formation. Meteorites, samples available for analysis in the lab, help constrain the timeline and conditions in the early Solar System. Asteroid reflectance spectra help define the links between asteroids and meteorites. Studies of the spectral types and sizes of asteroids test dynamical models. These studies also inform assessments of the impact hazard of near-Earth asteroids and the prospects of mining asteroids for commercial resources.

Observational work is reported. The visible ($\sim 0.55 - 0.90 \mu\text{m}$) reflectance spectra of 18 near-Earth asteroids (NEAs) and 3 Main Belt asteroids have been obtained with the 1.5-meter+FAST spectrograph at Mt Hopkins, AZ. The obtained spectra were The M4AST online spectral classification tool was implemented but has considerable limitations. We report preliminary spectral classifications.

A database of meteorite minerals is presented. A literature review was performed and a uniform database containing 66 meteorite minerals was compiled, of which 14 were later found to occur on Earth and 20 were later synthesized. 16 mineral properties are reported for each meteorite mineral, where available. The distribution of meteorite minerals across different meteorite groups is explored.

A database of iron meteorite trace element abundances is presented. A literature review was performed and a uniform database containing 708 iron meteorites was compiled. 16 trace elements (Cr, Co, Cu, Ga, Ge, As, Sb, W, Re, Ir, Pt, Pd, Rh, Ru, Os and Au) are reported for each iron meteorite, where available.

Mining metallic asteroids for platinum is explored. Iron meteorites with high PGE concentrations can be effectively selected with Ni abundance. Laser ablation, x-ray fluorescence and γ -ray spectroscopy methods for determining, statistically, the Pt content of a particular asteroid are discussed.

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1. Introduction

The first exoplanet, 51 Pegasi b, was discovered in 1995 (Mayor & Queloz, 1995). Exoplanet studies have now demolished the notion that planetary systems are rare (Muir, 2005). As of December 3, 2015, there were 1,916 confirmed planets distributed across 1288 planetary systems, of which 479 are multi-planet systems (NASA Exoplanet Archive¹, accessed January 2016). Furthermore, M dwarf stars (with radius $1-4R_{\oplus}$) are host to an average of 2.5 ± 0.2 planets, and about 1 in 4 low mass stars harbors a potentially habitable² Earth-sized planet (Dressing & Charbonneau, 2015). As a result we now have the prospect that life on another planet may be discovered in the near future (e.g. Linde, 2016).

Extrasolar planetary systems also illuminate the history of our own Solar System. The “nebular hypothesis” was first recorded in Emanuel Swedenborg’s *Principia* (1734). Immanuel Kant built upon Swedenborg’s work in *Universal Natural History and Theory of the Heavens* (1755). The nebular hypothesis was

independently proposed in 1796 by Pierre-Simon Laplace (Woolfson, 1993), who is now most frequently credited for the theory.

While it is now undisputed that our Solar System evolved from a protoplanetary nebula disk made of gas (99%wt) and dust (1%wt) (e.g. Apai and Laretta, 2010), the theory of its evolution is sparse in several areas. This introductory chapter describes what is known and what remains to be understood about the formation and history of our Solar System.

The field of planet formation studies the chemical make-up of protoplanetary disks, the conditions under which planets form, the types of planets that form and their respective histories, and whether it is possible for life to arise in other planetary systems. This field is a multidisciplinary area of research in input and scope, relying on many different forms of data. The four primary data sources in planet formation research are (1) the celestial bodies in our Solar System (including planets, moons, asteroids and comets), (2)

¹ <http://exoplanetarchive.ipac.caltech.edu>

² Here “habitable” was taken to mean Earth-sized and within the moist greenhouse inner limit and maximum greenhouse outer limit (Dressing & Charbonneau, 2015)

observations of extrasolar protoplanetary gas and dust disks, (3) computational simulations, and (4) laboratory analysis of meteorites, Moon rocks and other returned samples.

This thesis concentrates primarily on the composition of meteorites and asteroids and the links we can draw between them. Studies of the composition of meteorites and asteroids are vital in developing theories of planet formation, in assessing the impact hazard of near-Earth asteroids and in prospecting asteroids for future mining missions. The outline of this thesis is as follows:

- Chapter 1 introduces the topic of planet formation through the lens of current data and theory.
- Chapter 2 presents the analysis of optical spectra of near-Earth asteroids (NEAs) observed by both the FLWO/FAST spectrograph and the NEOWISE survey.
- Chapter 3 focuses on “meteorite minerals” These are exotic minerals that form only in the extreme pressure and temperature conditions of the early Solar System or the slowly cooling cores of planetesimals. Their properties may illuminate areas of uncertainty in planet formation theory. There isn't a database or catalogue of meteorite minerals in

the literature, so we created one. I look at where meteorite minerals are mostly found.

- Chapter 4 presents a comprehensive database of iron meteorite trace elements with the aim of finding patterns that can test existing classification schemes.
- Chapter 5 analyzes of the iron meteorite database in the context of potential future asteroid mining missions for precious metals.
- Chapter 6 summarizes the main results and notes areas for further work.

1.1 PLANET FORMATION CHRONOLGY

Theories of planet formation and evolution rely heavily on geophysical and astrophysical data. There is now more data than ever before, with thousands of candidate planetary systems to study. This section will focus on the physical processes that lead interstellar clouds to collapse, first forming stars and then planets.

1.1.1 Stellar Birth in the ISM

Spiral galaxies, including the Milky Way, contain interstellar clouds of gas and dust that are visible via far IR and mm-wavelength astronomy (Strafella et al., 2005). Pre-main sequence stars were first discovered in the Taurus, Auriga and Orion dense interstellar clouds (e.g. Kenyon et al.,

2008b). These discoveries led towards the understanding that stars form in these giant clouds (e.g. Kenyon et al., 2008b).

Sir James Jeans (1877-1946) investigated the conditions that must be met for star formation to occur in these clouds. Jeans (1902) pointed out that a cloud will become unstable and collapse when it has insufficient gaseous pressure support to balance the force of gravity. He found that, at a given temperature, T (Kelvin), and mass density (ρ_0) a cloud (or a region within a cloud) is stable at sufficiently small masses. The resulting Jeans criterion is that collapse will occur if $M_C > M_J$ where M_C is cloud mass and M_J is the *Jeans Mass*:

$$M_J \simeq \left(\frac{5kT}{Gm_H} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \left(\frac{3}{4\pi\rho_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

where k is the Boltzmann constant, T is temperature, G is the gravitational constant, m_H is the mass of a gas particle and ρ_0 is the gas density of the cloud.

Within interstellar gas and dust clouds, when the Jeans criterion is satisfied locally, that portion of the cloud begins to collapse and fragment (e.g. Carroll and Ostlie, 2007). The most massive regions collapse rapidly (Bernasconi and Maeder, 1996), evolving into high mass stars on the upper end of the main sequence.

Within 10-20 Myr the most massive stars have evolved off the main sequence and end their lives in supernovae explosions (Schaller et al., 1992). Protoplanetary disks lose all of their gaseous contents by an age of ~ 10 Myr, hence giant planets must form on this timescale or less (D'Angelo et al., 2010). Rocky planets formation timescales are constrained by studies of primitive meteorites (Righter and O'Brien, 2011). These planets form on timescales of 10 - 100 Myr after the initial collapse of the central star (Righter and O'Brien, 2011), and may therefore be inhibited from forming around high mass stars (Yin et al., 2002). Less massive stars live ~ 100 Myr - 10 Gyr or more on the main sequence (Schaller et al., 1992) and so can host planetary systems.

1.1.2 Protoplanetary Disks

Protoplanetary disks are composed of cold dust and gas and are detectable with infrared photometry. Until the late 1970s, the presence of protoplanetary disks were inferred from stellar formation models (e.g. Safronov, 1967). The first direct evidence in favor of Laplace's nebular hypothesis came in the late 1970s. The T Tauri stars were already known for being strong sources of infrared radiation (Mendoza, 1966). At least

half of the 500 T Tauri stars studied by Cohen and Kuhn (1979) showed an excess of infrared radiation ($\lambda < 20 \mu\text{m}$) attributable only as the thermal emission of hot dust grains.

Recent observations show that nearly every young ($< \text{few Myr}$) star has an optically thick circumstellar disk from which planets will form over a few Myr (Williams & Cieza, 2011). The 1983 launch of the Infrared Astronomical Satellite (IRAS) opened up the mid-IR sky (12 - 100 μm) and revealed cold circumstellar dust with temperatures of a few tens of degrees K (Rucinski, 1985). Not long after, millimeter wavelength observations showed that many disks contained large dust grains and molecules (Weintraub, Sandell & Duncan 1989) and had sufficient material to form planetary systems on the scale of our own (Beckwith et al. 1990). These discoveries led a new field of research that tries to connect the birth of stars to the birth of planets.

To conserve angular momentum during the core contraction of isothermal cloud, the gaseous nebula begins to rotate more rapidly (Terebey et al., 1984). With an increased rate of rotation, the remaining gas and dust collapses onto a point source. As more material with higher angular momentum falls inward, a rotating disk is formed (Williams and Cieza, 2011). Early in its

Figure 1.1 - HST images of the protoplanetary disk 114-426 in six photometric filters, equivalent to the standard U , B , V , $H\alpha$, I , and z passbands (Miotello et al., 2012)

evolution, the disk loses mass by accretion onto the star (Gorti et al., 2009). Photoevaporation of the outer disk restricts the diameter of the disk to several hundreds of AU centered around the young star (Williams and Cieza, 2011). Deep Hubble Space Telescope (HST) broadband images show these dusty disks as shadows against the bright background nebula (Figure 1.1). The protoplanetary disks observed around young stars are similar in size and mass to that from which our Solar System formed (Lada, 1999).

The growth of dust grains in protoplanetary disks is the first stage of planet formation (Beckwith et al., 2000). The solid composition of the terrestrial planets and the cores of the giant planets require that the aggregation of planets involved the accretion of the solid dust

particles within the protoplanetary disks onto larger bodies, called “planetesimals”.

Radiation from the young star causes water ice within some radius of the star to sublime, leaving behind only solid particles (Faure and Mensing, 2007). This radius is called the “snow line” and is dependent upon the luminosity of the star, as well as the disk surface density, mass accretion rate and opacity (e.g. Lecar et al., 2005). Within the snow line, collisions between dust particles in the protoplanetary disk continue up to form meter-scale rocks.

While dust grains are in the (sub-)micron-size range, collisions between dust grains are mainly caused by Brownian Motion (Wurm and Blum, 2006). Particle-particle collision lab experiments determined the strength of the adhesion forces of silicate, SiO_2 , particles and water-ice particles to be on the order of 10^{-7} ergs and 10^{-6} ergs, respectively (Heim et al., 1999; Dominik and Tielens, 1997). A similar experiment explores collisions between single particles and flat targets and between dust aggregates composed of mono-disperse silica spheres and irregularly shaped grains of diamond, enstatite, and silicon carbide (Poppe et al., 2000a). These experiments determined that μm -sized dust

particles colliding with velocities below 1 m/s will adhere to each other instantly while collisions with greater velocity will typically rebound. With sufficiently gentle collisions, dust aggregates will form and grow with more of these “hit-and-stick” collisions.

The growth of dust grains has been directly observed in nearby stellar systems. Disks with larger 0.1 - 0.2 μm interstellar grains become more transparent with increasing wavelength, as short wavelength visible light is scattered more efficiently than long wavelengths (Kim et al., 1994). HST images of the Orion nebula’s largest disk, 114-426, in the visual and near-IR wavelengths show that the 114-426 disk has a translucent edge 5 to 10 times more opaque than expected and cannot be fit with standard interstellar extinction curves (Throop et al., 2001). Extinction in 114-426 must be dominated by particles have grown to radii larger than $5\mu\text{m}$ (Throop et al., 2001). The absence of millimeter-wavelength emission, in combination with grain growth models in 114-426 suggests that this disk has a lower emissivity ($2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) than the previously assumed interstellar emissivity ($2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) (Throop et al., 2001; Mundy et al., 1995). This is evidence that the grains that have

grown to diameters beyond a few millimeters (Throop et al., 2001).

The next growth stage is problematic. There is little consensus about how rocks grow from meter sizes into planetesimals of ≥ 100 km diameter. This is one of the greatest puzzles in planet formation theory.

Planetesimal is the designation given to small (meter to 100-km scale) astronomical bodies. When planetesimals collide with one another and form moon-sized bodies (≥ 3000 km diameter) they are then called “protoplanets”.

As they grow, protoplanets increase in their central temperature due mainly to radioactive decay to heat (Šrámek et al., 2012). The short-lived radionuclides aluminum-26 (with a half life, $T_{1/2} = 0.73$ Myr) and iron-60 ($T_{1/2} = 2.6$ Myr) are primarily responsible for the heating of protoplanets (e.g. Hevey and Sanders, 2006; Sahijpal et al., 2007). Protoplanets also undergo heating by impacts. Large protoplanets (e.g. $R > 900$ km) are mostly heated by deposition of gravitational energy, while the heating of smaller bodies is dominated by the thermal energy of impactors (Šrámek et al., 2012).

As a result of this heating, the protoplanets become liquid and differentiate, with

high Z elements, mainly iron, and siderophile (“iron-loving”) elements, sinking to the core of the body, leaving low Z elements behind to form a silicate mantle and crust (e.g. Šrámek et al., 2011). The Earth and the Moon are similarly differentiated.

1.2 ASTEROIDS

Planet formation is not 100% efficient. In our Solar System some planetesimals were unable to form planets and they have left behind remnants known as asteroids (e.g. Bottke et al., 2006). By studying asteroids we gain insight into what planetesimals were like 4.5 Gyr ago.

Due to their small size (≤ 1000 km), dark surfaces (albedo ≤ 0.25) and low (≤ 300 K) temperatures, asteroids have only ever been detected in our Solar system. They are found in three main locations, the Main Belt and the Kuiper Belt. The Main Belt is located between 2.2 - 3.2 AU (Figure 1.2). During planet formation, Jupiter’s gravity perturbed planetesimals in this region and prevented them forming another planet (Petit et al., 2001). The most recent description of the compositional structure of the asteroid Main Belt is given in DeMeo et al. (2015) and is summarized here:

Figure 1.2 - The orbits of the major planets are shown in blue: the current location of the major planets is indicated by large colored dots. The locations of the minor planets, including numbered and multiple-apparition/long-arc unnumbered objects, are indicated by green circles. Objects with perihelia within 1.3 AU are shown by red circles. The two "clouds" of objects 60° ahead and behind Jupiter (and at or near Jupiter's distance from the sun) are the Jupiter Trojans, here colored deep blue. Numbered periodic comets are shown as filled light-blue squares. Other comets are shown as unfilled light-blue squares. In this view, objects in direct orbits move counterclockwise and the vernal equinox is towards the right. The plot is correct for December 12, 2015. Plot prepared by the Minor Planet Center.

The *Inner Main Belt* (2.0-2.5 AU) is dominated by of V-type and S-type asteroids (DeMeo, 2015). C-type asteroids make up only 6% of the total mass of large ($D > 100$ km) asteroids and 25% of medium size ($20 \text{ km} < D < 100 \text{ km}$) asteroids (DeMeo, 2015). For the smallest sizes ($5 \text{ km} < D < 20 \text{ km}$), C- and S-type asteroids are present in roughly equal quantity.

In the *Middle Main Belt* (2.5-2.82 AU), the largest objects are the C- and B-type asteroids, which comprise roughly 31% and 7%, respectively, of the entire Main Belt by mass. At $5 \text{ km} < D < 20 \text{ km}$ the taxonomic makeup Middle Belt is roughly identical to the Inner Belt.

The *Outer Main Belt* (2.82-3.3 AU) is dominated by C-complex asteroids. The relative

fraction of S-complex asteroids in the Outer Main Belt is small, but their total mass is still quite significant given that the mass in the Outer Belt is 2-10 times greater than in the Inner Belt at each size range.

Jupiter Trojans is the collective name for two compact groups of asteroids that formed around the L4 and L5 Lagrangian points (Figure 1.2; Vinogradova and Chernetenko, 2015). The Jupiter Trojans have a heliocentric orbit and are in a 1:1 resonance with Jupiter (Vinogradova and Chernetenko, 2015). More than 1900 Jupiter Trojans are known (Dotto et al., 2006) and they have a total estimated mass of $(0.30 \pm 0.19) \times 10^{-10} M_{\text{Sun}}$, accounting for the ~7% estimated Trojans that haven't yet been discovered (Vinogradova and Chernetenko, 2015). The group at L4 has mass of $(0.19 \pm 0.11) \times 10^{-10} M_{\text{Sun}}$, making it a factor 1.7 larger than the group at L5 which has mass $(0.11 \pm 0.07) \times 10^{-10} M_{\text{Sun}}$ (Vinogradova and Chernetenko, 2015). The Jupiter Trojans are “strongly homogeneous” and are dominated by D-type asteroids (Dotto et al., 2006). The origin of these bodies is still poorly understood.

The Kuiper Belt lies much further from the Sun and is broader at 30-55 AU. However, taking the ratio of the width to the heliocentric distance for each asteroid belt, the Kuiper Belt is only a

factor of 1.83 broader than the Main Belt. Like the Main Belt, the Kuiper Belt is thought to consist of remnant planetesimals from the protoplanetary disk that formed the Solar System (e.g. Delsanti and Jewitt, 2006). Many, but not all Kuiper Belt Objects (KBOs) are in stable resonance orbits with Neptune (e.g. Chiang et al., 2003, Kavelaars et al., 2008). Favored models suggest the formation of the Kuiper Belt is a result of earlier instability in the orbits of Uranus and Neptune (e.g. Levison et al., 2008) but the precise origins remain unclear.

1.2.1 Taxonomy and classification

Asteroid taxonomies have been developed as a means to group asteroids of similar composition. However, asteroid composition cannot be measured in detail, as samples for lab analysis are not available. Asteroids are instead studied via telescopic spectroscopy or photometry in the near-infrared (1-2.5 μm) and visible (0.3-1.0 μm) bands (e.g. DeMeo et al., 2009).

Incident sunlight on an asteroid is scattered, and some fraction of this light reaches our telescopes. The *albedo* of an asteroid is the ratio of observed Solar flux that is reflected from the surface to the total incident Solar flux incident on

the body. The bulk composition and constituent minerals most influence the albedo of an object (Thomas et al., 2011). Physical properties of an object's surface, such as the degree of space weathering and the grain size distribution, also affect the albedo of an object (Thomas et al., 2011).

The albedo of asteroid is required to convert the absolute magnitude (H) to the size (Harris and Harris, 1997). Understanding the size distribution and the average size of certain populations test dynamical models (e.g. Bottke et al., 2001) and inform impact hazard assessments (e.g. Stuart and Binzel, 2004).

Certain wavelengths are absorbed depending on the surface composition of the asteroid. This absorption produces signatures that can be detected in their reflection spectra. From these absorption features we can detect signatures of some silicates and water on the surface of the asteroid (e.g. McCord and Gaffey, 1974).

1.2.1.1 A Brief History of Asteroid Taxonomies

Asteroids are grouped into similar classes in an evolving set of taxonomic schemes. Taxonomic classification systems for asteroids

have existed since there was enough spectral data to distinguish meaningful groups.

The first taxonomies were based on asteroid broad-band photometric colors (e.g. Wood & Kuiper, 1963; Chapman et al., 1971) where objects were divided into either the "S" (stony) or "C" (carbonaceous) class.

The Eight-Color Asteroid Survey (ECAS, Zellner et al., 1985) data led to the development of the Tholen taxonomy (1984). The Tholen taxonomy was developed primarily using the ECAS broad-band spectrophotometric colors. Measurements of albedo were included to distinguish some of the class boundaries. The taxonomy consists of 14 classes, including the two major C- and S-type classes, and are each denoted by a single letter.

The second phase of the Small Main-Belt Asteroid Spectroscopic Survey (SMASSII) obtained visible wavelength reflection spectra (0.4 to 1.0 μm) of 1189 Main Belt asteroids in the distance range 2.690 to 2.815 AU (Bus, 1999). This led to the Bus-Binzel SMASSII spectral taxonomy (Bus, 1999; Bus and Binzel, 2002a, 2002b). The SMASSII taxonomy consists of 26 spectral types (Figure 1.3). The defining spectral

features of the SMASSII taxonomy are the following:

- slope (“redish”, neutral or “bluish”)
- peak reflectance, (how broad or narrow the peak is)
- subtle absorption features
- 1 μm feature (how deep or shallow)

The MIT-UH-IRTF program³, using more advanced IR detectors, led to increased availability of asteroid spectra extending into the near-infrared wavelengths (0.8 to 2.5 μm). The near-IR data range contains additional diagnostic compositional information because of the presence of features at 1 and 2 μm , primarily due to the presence of olivine and pyroxene (DeMeo et al., 2009). The increased availability of near-IR data led to the development of the Bus-DeMeo taxonomy, which spans both optical and near-IR wavelengths from 0.45 to 2.45 μm (DeMeo et al., 2009). The Bus-DeMeo taxonomy and has a total of 24 asteroid sub-types divided into the S-complex, C-complex, X-complex and “End Members” (Figure 1.3). In the Bus-DeMeo taxonomy three classes from the earlier SMASSII taxonomy are eliminated (Sl, Sk, Ld) and one (Sv) created. A “w” notation was also added to

flag objects having similar spectral features but differing only by having a higher spectral slope.

Bus (2002) provides a review of the evolution of asteroid taxonomies.

1.2.1.1 Asteroid Spectral Features

The proposed taxonomies are based on spectral features and have physical meaning. The main three asteroid spectral types are the S-complex, C-complex and X-complex which refer to stony, carbonaceous and metallic compositions, respectively. Here we describe some major features of the asteroid spectra from 0.45-2.45 μm as discussed in DeMeo et al. (2009).

S-complex spectra have two features, one at 1 μm and the other at 2 μm . The main difference between the classes of the S-complex is the width of the 1- μm absorption and the depths of the 2 μm feature. These strong absorption features are credited to the silicate composition of S-complex asteroids, linking them to stony meteorites.

C-complex spectra have a linear, neutral to slightly positive slope. The Cg-, Cgh- and Ch-types have a pronounced UV drop off. The Cg- and Cgh-types asteroids have a shallow absorption band centered near 0.7 μm . The 0.7

³ <http://smass.mit.edu/minus.html>

Figure 1.3 - (Left) key showing all 26 SMASSII taxonomic classes defined over 0.40–1.0 μm . The spectra are arranged in a pattern that approximates the class location in spectral component (PCA) space. The horizontal lines to which each spectrum is referenced has a reflectance value of unity. (Right) key showing all 24 Bus-DeMeo taxonomic classes defined over 0.45–2.45 μm . The average spectra are plotted with constant horizontal and vertical scaling and are arranged in a way that approximates the relative position of each class in the primary spectral component space defined by slope, PC1, and PC2. The horizontal lines to which each spectrum is referenced has a reflectance value of unity.

μm feature is thought to be a sign of hydration (Rivkin et al., 2006).

X-complex spectra are relatively linear, featureless and have a red slope which may be attributed to the high reflectivity of metals (Shepard et al., 2010), linking X-complex asteroids to metallic meteorites. The Xe-type has an absorption band short-ward of 0.55 μm and the Xk-type is slightly curved downward and with a faint feature between 0.8-1.0 μm .

1.2.1.1 PCA Analysis

Modern asteroid taxonomic systems evoke Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to

define boundaries between classes and sub-classes (Bus and Binzel, 2002; DeMeo et al., 2009). The central idea in PCA is to reduce the dimensionality of a data set by defining eigenvectors for the system that can describe the whole system as the summation of scaled eigenvectors (Jolliffe, 2002). The eigenvectors, or *principal components* (PCs) are ordered so that the first few retain most of the variation present in all of the original variables (Jolliffe, 2002). PCA was first used for asteroid classification by Tholen (1984).

As discussed in DeMeo et al. (2009), the most striking feature seen within the principal

Figure 1.4 - From DeMeo et al., (2009): Results for PC2' versus PC1'. All objects plotted are labeled with their taxonomic classification in this system. Line α separates objects with and without 2- μ m absorption bands. The direction orthogonal to line α (increasing PC2' values) indicates deeper 2- μ m and narrower 1- μ m absorption bands. The direction parallel to line α (increasing PC1' values) indicates wider 1- μ m absorption bands. The notation "PC1'", "PC2'", etc. denotes that these principal components are computed after removal of the slope.

component space is the large gap in PC1' versus PC2' space (Figure 1.4). This clear boundary distinguishes between spectra that have a 2- μ m absorption band (the S-complex and the A-, V-, K-, L-, Q-, R- and O-types) and those that do not (the C- and C-complexes and the D-, L-, T- and B-types)

1.2.2 Near-Earth Asteroids

Near-Earth asteroids (NEAs) are defined as having a perihelion distance $q < 1.3$ AU and aphelion distance $Q > 0.983$ AU (Morbidelli et al., 2002). The NEA population is transient with

timescales of order 10 Myr (Gladman et al., 2000). NEAs are supplied from the Main Belt via resonances with Jupiter (Morbidelli et al., 2002). The numbers and distribution of NEAs can then test these models. Due to their relative proximity, NEAs are the source of most of the retrieved meteorites on Earth (e.g. Thomas & Binzel, 2010).

The NEAs are split into three orbital subgroups, *Amor*, *Apollo* and *Aten* asteroids shown in Figure 1.5 (Shoemaker et al., 1979). These orbital subgroups are summarized in Table 1.1.

Earth-crossing NEAs, *Atens*, are particularly interesting because they are

Figure 1.5 - NEA orbital sub-groups with the Amors in orange, Apollos in pink, Atens in green and the orbits of Earth and Mars in blue and red, respectively.

potentially hazardous objects (PHOs) that could collide with Earth. NEAs of sufficient size (≥ 1 km diameter) could pose a serious threat to life on Earth. This concern has motivated research into how many there are and how frequently they collide with Earth (e.g. Stuart and Binzel, 2004). Estimates of hazardous impact frequency require knowledge of total population of NEAs, their orbits, (size) frequency distribution, mass and tensile strength (Yeomans, 2013).

Table 1.1 - Orbital type and semi-major axis for all near-Earth asteroids and Mars-crossing asteroids (Morbidelli et al., 2002).

Orbit	Defining Parameters
Amor	$1.0167 > q > 1.30$
Apollo	$a \geq 1.0, q \leq 1.0167$
Atens	$a < 1.0, Q > 0.983$

1.2.2.1 NEA Properties

Despite the importance of NEAs for dynamical Solar System models and for impact hazard assessment, detailed information on NEAs is sparse. Accurate orbits, sizes, rotation periods and spectra are available for fewer than 10% of the now >14,000 known NEAs (Galache et al.,

2015). The number of known NEAs is increasing at a rate of $\sim 1,500$ /year, mainly from the Catalina⁴ and Pan-STARRS⁵ wide-field optical surveys (Minor Planet Center⁶ data). Meanwhile, the MIT-IRTF programme⁷, the largest program for optical-near-IR spectroscopy, acquires NEA spectra at a significantly slower rate of ~ 100 /year.

Radar is the only direct technique for NEA diameter measurement. Radar has high accuracy, however the integration time needed to achieve any given signal-to-noise ratio for a given target increases as $R_{\text{tar}}^8 A^{-4}$, where R_{tar} the geocentric distance to the asteroid and A is the cross-sectional area of the asteroid (Olsen et al., 2002). This is why radar observations are often limited to NEAs that make close (< 0.1 AU) flybys of the Earth. Furthermore, the 305-m Arecibo telescope and the 70-m Goldstone antenna (DSS-14) are almost entirely responsible for the history of asteroid radar, which has limited rate of NEA observations (Olsen et al., 2002).

The most common method for diameter determination employs the absolute magnitude of the asteroids and a range of assumed albedos (P_V),

⁴ <http://www.lpl.arizona.edu/css/>

⁵ <http://pan-starrs.ifa.hawaii.edu/public/>

⁶ <http://www.minorplanetcenter.net>

⁷ <http://smass.mit.edu/minus.html>

typically 5–25% (Fowler & Chillemi, 1992). Optical discovery surveys measure V-band magnitudes. Given an orbit, this can be converted into an absolute magnitude, H , where H is the V-band magnitude the object would have if viewed at 1 AU at zero solar phase angle when the asteroid is 1 AU from the sun (Harris and D’Abramo, 2015). To convert H to a diameter, D , we use the relation (Bowell et al., 1989):

$$D = (1329 \text{ km} * 10^{-H/5}) / \sqrt{P_V}$$

A diameter of 1.0 km is equivalent to an absolute magnitude $H = 17.75$ for $P_V = 0.14$ (Stuart and Binzel, 2004; Stokes et al., 2003, Harris & D’Abramo, 2015). However, the uncertainty associated with this technique due to unknown albedos is a factor of 2.2 in diameter which corresponds to a factor of 11 in volume and mass.

A better method is to use the thermal, quasi-black body emission of the asteroid. However viewing geometry and thermal inertia combine on these rotating bodies to complicate the measurement.

Infrared methods are more promising because thermal black body is directly related to size of the asteroid via the Planck Formula:

$$B_\lambda(\lambda, T) = \frac{2hc^2}{\lambda^5} \frac{1}{e^{hc/(\lambda k_B T)} - 1}$$

where B_λ is the blackbody function, h is Planck’s constant, k_B is Boltzmann’s constant, c is the speed of light, T is temperature and λ is wavelength. Reddy et al. (2012) discuss various radiometric methods to constrain the albedo and diameters of NEAs based on thermal flux. These include the “Standard Thermal Model” (STM) (Lebofsky and Spencer, 1989), the “Fast Rotating Model” (FRM) (Lebofsky et al., 1978) and the Near-Earth Asteroid Thermal Model (NEATM) (Harris, 1998).

In 2010 the Wide-field Infrared Survey Explorer (WISE) mission completed a mid-infrared survey of the entire sky in 4 bands centered at 3.4, 4.6, 12 and 22 μm (Wright et al., 2010). The NEOWISE IR survey (Mainzer et al., 2011) used the WISE data to search for asteroids. They estimate a NEA population of 981 ± 19 for $D > 1 \text{ km}$ and $20,500 \pm 3000$ for $D > 100 \text{ m}$ (Mainzer et al., 2011). This result prompted Harris and D’Abramo (2015) to re-examine their earlier results. Their revised estimates match the NEOWISE results (Harris and D’Abramo, 2015).

1.2.3 Space Weathering, NEAs and Meteorites

Two thirds of the NEAs and MCAs are comprised of stony, S-complex, asteroids (Binzel

Figure 1.6 - Reflectance spectra of ordinary chondrite meteorites compared with asteroids grouped according to taxonomic types (Binzel et al., 2010).

at al., 2004). This presents an interesting discrepancy, as S-complex asteroids are linked to LL chondrite meteorites. But these comprise only 8.7% of all retrieved meteorites (Vernazza et al., 2008). Ordinary chondritic meteorites, which represent 80% of all retrieved meteorites (Ruzicka, 2009) are linked to Q-type asteroids (Figure 1.6) which represent only ~1% of all classified asteroids⁸ and are only observed in the NEA population (Chapman et al., 1996).

This discrepancy is now attributed to “space weathering”. Space weathering is a process that reddens asteroid surfaces on timescales of as little as 50,000 years (Hapke, 2001). The underlying cause of these alterations in spectral reflectance is the production of nano-phase Fe on the surfaces of grains (Pieters et al.,

2000; Sasaki et al., 2001) by micrometeoroids and solar wind particles (Chapman, 2004),

In situ spacecraft measurements by NEAR-Shoemaker of the S-type asteroid 433 Eros revealed that it was a weathered Q-type and therefore that it had ordinary chondrite composition (McCoy et al., 2001). Hence, if many S-types are in fact weathered Q-types, then they may be sufficiently abundant to account for the dominance of ordinary chondrites in the meteorite flux (McCoy et al., 2001). However, the relative rarity of telescopic Q-type NEAs remained unexplained. The few observed spectral matches lie nearly exclusively among the NEA population (e.g. Chapman, 1996). Ordinary chondrite spectral matches are effectively absent among Main Belt asteroids.

It is now understood that space weathering confused the interpretation of the association between ordinary chondritic meteorites with S-type asteroids. This decades-long problem was resolved in Binzel et al. (2010) which found that the Q-type NEAs had undergone an Earth encounter closer than the Earth-to-Moon distance within the past 5×10^5 years. They determined that close encounters with Earth and

⁸ "JPL Small-Body Database Search Engine: spec. type = Q (SMASSII)". JPL Solar System Dynamics. Retrieved 2016-04-02.

Mars (within ~16 Earth radii) can “refresh” the surface of asteroids via tidal stress. The resulting redistribution of surface material exposes fresh, unweathered regolith, creating the spectral change from S- to Q-type.

1.3 Meteoroids and Meteorites

When asteroids collide with one another they are often shattered into smaller pieces. If these pieces are between 10 μm and 1 m in diameter, then they are known as *meteoroids* (Rubin and Grossman, 2009). More than 80% of meteoroids entering the atmosphere are between 10^{-7} - 10^{-3} g (Flynn, 2002). The total meteoroid mass flux onto the Earth is around 44 tonnes/day (Hughes, 1978).

Meteoroids that enter Earth’s atmosphere are heated due to friction, exciting the atoms of the meteoroid material. Most meteoroids enter between speeds of ~10 km/sec and ~75 km/sec (Younger et al., 2012). Those meteoroids that are larger than 0.01 mm usually produce a visible bright streak of light known as a *meteor*, but the exact size depends on the entry velocity (Ceplecha et al., 1998). The light is produced by atoms returning to their unexcited state. Larger meteoroids (> 10 cm dia.) may reach the ground at while the smaller meteoroids (\leq 10 cm dia.)

disintegrate as they enter the atmosphere (Klekociuk et al., 2005).

The remnants of meteoroids on Earth are known as *meteorites*. Typically 1-25% of the original mass of a meteoroid that survives the passage to Earth becomes a meteorite (Ceplecha et al., 1998). Liberman et al. (2002) estimate that the Campo del Cielo meteorite, which weighs over 1000 kg, originally came from a meteoroid with a mass of at least 840,000 kg, only 0.1% reached the ground.

As meteorites are remnants of asteroids, their chemical composition and structure provide a useful way to study asteroid composition and places constraints on the conditions and the time at which the asteroids formed. No other branch of astronomy has access to la investigations.

1.3.1 Meteorite Measurement Techniques

Meteorites come in a wide variety of chemical and structural types. This variety is investigated of using a number of different techniques that have been developed or adapted to suit the specific analytical needs of meteoriticists.

1.3.1.1 Radiometric Dating

The principle of radioactive dating relies on the initial content of a particular radioactive

Figure 1.7 - From Hernández-Bernal and Solé, 2014: K-Ar and Ar-Ar ages of about 200 undifferentiated and differentiated meteorites and lunar rocks. Most of the plotted points are whole rock ages but in some cases correspond to chondrule or matrix ages. The most significant feature is that achondrites and lunar rocks report ages between 4.0 and 3.0 Ga (with one exception), but not younger, whereas L, LL and H chondrites show a wider range.

(unstable) isotope in a geological sample and its half-life ($t_{1/2}$) (Allegre, 2008). With measurements of the current abundance of that radioisotope, the time that has passed since the formation of the geological sample can be determined. This method is called *isotopic dating* or *radioactive dating*. However, it is difficult to accurately determine the initial amount of a radioisotope. This challenge is overcome with a technique called *parent-daughter* isotopic dating (Allegre, 2008). Parent-daughter isotopic dating involves measuring the quantity of the stable isotope

(“daughter”) that is a decay product of the radionuclide (“parent”) in a geological sample (Allegre, 2008). The parent and daughter abundances are then measured and the initial abundance of the parent isotope is calculated, allowing for the calculation of the age of the sample (Allegre, 2008).

We can place chronological constraints on events in the early solar system using now-extinct radionuclides. Due to their short half-lives, the extinct radionuclide chronometers have high time resolutions, but they provide only relative ages

(Hibiya et al., 2014). Dating methods based on extinct radionuclides are calibrated with the U-Pb method to give absolute ages (Allegré, 2008). The D'Orbigny meteorite (4564.42 ± 0.12 Ma) is used as a standard for this conversion, as high precision dating with the U-Pb method and with various short-lived radionuclides has been performed on this meteorite (Amelin, 2008).

At the beginning of the solar system, there were several relatively short-lived radionuclides like ^{26}Al , ^{60}Fe , ^{53}Mn , and ^{129}I present within the solar nebula (Lee et al., 1977; Shukolyukov and Lugmair, 1993; Trinquier et al., 2008; Reynolds, 1960). Meteorites are ideal specimens for delineating the early history of the solar system and providing an absolute ages of the solar system as many form within the first Gyr (Figure 1.7; Hernández-Bernal and Solé, 2014). Some common isotopes used for dating meteorites include⁹:

- ^{26}Al - ^{29}Mg (Lee et al., 1977)
- ^{60}Fe - ^{60}Ni (Shukolyukov and Lugmair, 1993)
- ^{182}Hf - ^{182}W (Harper and Jackson, 1994)
- ^{187}Re - β - ^{187}Os (Allegré and Luck, 1980)
- ^{238}U - ^{204}Pb (Göpel et al., 1994)
- ^{40}K - ^{40}Ar (Aldrich and Nier, 1948a)

- ^{53}Mn - ^{53}Cr (Birck et al., 1999)
- ^{129}I - ^{129}Xe (Reynolds, 1960)

1.3.1.2 Neutron Activation Analysis

Instrumental Neutron Activation Analysis (INAA) is used to determine the mass fraction and relative abundance of trace elements in meteorites.

INAA is the preferred technique, especially for iron meteorites, because it is sensitive on the order of parts per billion and can be used to measure up 74 trace elements at a time. INAA is also non-destructive.

Figure 1.8 - Gamma-ray spectra of neutron activated tungsten-molybdenum catalyst at two decay times (Guinn and Wagner, 1960)

⁹ This is not an exhaustive list but represents the more frequently used dating methods.

This technique involves irradiating small, typically 10-100 mg, samples in the core of a nuclear reactor (Shirai et al, 2015). INAA can use either a short irradiation, which may be as little as 10s, or a long irradiation, which may last as long as 12 hours depending on the bulk composition of the sample in order to get a good signal-to-noise on the isotopes of interest (Michael Ames, priv. comm.).

INAA exploits neutron capture reactions. In neutron capture reactions, the nucleus of an atom accepts an additional neutron, putting it in an excited and unstable state. The nucleus quickly decays to the ground state, emitting one or more gamma-rays at characteristic energies between 10 keV - 2.75 MeV¹⁰.

Irradiated, and now decaying, samples are then placed near gamma-ray detectors and abundance is determined from the gamma-ray signatures (Figure 1.8; Guinn and Wagner, 1960). Gamma-ray detectors record the elemental and isotopic emission line energies and intensities. Intensities are calibrated using samples of known composition irradiated in the same way. Abundances are then determined.

1.3.1.3 Cosmic Ray Exposure Age

Cosmic Ray Exposure (CRE) age is used in studying all types of meteorites. CRE age is defined as the length of time between the collision that ejects the meter-sized meteoroids from the asteroid body and the time that the final meteorite strikes the Earth (Herzog, 2003). When the meteorite eventually reaches Earth surface, the atmosphere protects it from further radiation.

The principle behind the CRE parameter is that the great majority of the material in a ~100 km-sized planetesimal is buried under many meters of dense material that screens out cosmic rays (Eugster et al., 2003). When the parent asteroid is involved in a collision that shatters all or part of the asteroid, it sends meteoroids on a trajectory of their own, orbiting the Sun. These meteoroids are now exposed to cosmic radiation. Cosmic rays can be highly energetic. For energies > 5 MeV they give rise to cosmogenic stable and radioactive nuclides (Eugster et al., 2002). Nuclear reactions which leave detectable signatures such as the relative isotopic abundances of ³⁸Ar and ³⁹Ar (Cobb, 1966) and ³⁹K, ⁴⁰K and ⁴¹K (Shankar et al., 2011). Longer exposure to cosmic rays increases the ³⁸Ar/³⁹Ar

¹⁰ https://dspace.mit.edu/bitstream/handle/1721.1/73642/12-119-spring-2006/contents/lecture-notes/week4_5.pdf

Figure 1.9 - CRE age distributions for carbonaceous chondrites. Eugster et al., (2003).

and $^{39}\text{K}/^{40}\text{K}/^{41}\text{K}$ ratios. These abundance ratios can then be measured using INAA (Section 1.3.1.1).

The effective duration of cosmic-ray bombardment (the CRE age) can be determined if the concentration and production rate of a stable nuclide are known (Eugster et al., 2002).

CRE age distributions within a class of meteorites can be interpreted as major collisions

of the parent body that result in the release of many meteoroids (Eugster, 2002). The distribution of CRE ages varies significantly between meteorite classes (Figure 1.9). For instance, most iron meteorites have CRE ages up to 1 Gyr, while stony meteorites have an average CRE age of 120 Myr (Eugster et al., 2002).

1.3.2 Classification System

To make the enormous variety of meteorites more tractable, meteoriticists have developed a classification system for meteorites based on their chemical compounds, elemental composition, mineralogy and structure (e.g. Maurette, 2006). The classification of meteorites seeks to minimize the total number of categories without lumping together unrelated meteorites (Wasson, 1974). The minimum number of meteorites necessary to propose a novel *group* is typically 5 (Wasson, 1974). Meteorites within a group have tightly delineated elemental abundance relationships (e.g. Figure 1.13) and share structural groups.

With increasingly sophisticated analysis and larger numbers of meteorites included, the most broadly accepted classification system has evolved into 45 *groups*, and 20 *clans* that link

Figure 1.10 - Diagram expressing the systematics of meteorite classification and showing the major meteorite divisions, classes, clans, and groups and relationships among meteorite groups. URE — ureilite, ACA — acapulcoite, LOD — lodranite, ANG — angrite, AUB — aubrite, BRA — brachinite, WIN — winonite, HED — howardite-eucrite-diogenite, MES — mesosiderite, MG PAL — main-group pallasite, ES PAL — Eagle Station pallasite, PP PAL — pyroxene pallasite, SHE — shergottite, NAK — nakhlite, CHA — chassignite, OPX — orthopyroxenite. (Weisburg et al., 2006).

similar groups together (Figure 1.10, Weisburg et al., 2006). Clans are collected into two major categories, the *chondrites* and *achondrites* (Weisburg et al., 2006). The system has also been refined to minimize the number of groups where new data has provided reason to group them together, such as in the case of IIA and IIB irons, that are now considered a single group, IIAB.

The chondrites are undifferentiated meteorites. Most achondrites are differentiated meteorites with the exception of the *primitive achondrites* which are not differentiated but still do not contain chondrules. Achondrites have trimodal metal-content peaks at 1, 50 and 99% (Wasson, 1974). These three peaks different structures (*primitive achondrite* class, *stony-irons* and *iron* clan, respectively, see Section 1.3.2). The term “stony-irons” is no longer in favor as an official class but it is a useful descriptive term for the mesosiderite and pallasite clans which are both roughly half iron and half silicate. They contain 208 and 61 members, respectively.

Alternative classification schemes have been proposed on the basis of more recently linked meteorite groups (e.g. Weisburg et al., 2006) but none have yet been widely adopted. This thesis uses the current standard classification scheme.

In the following sections (1.3.3, 1.3.4, 1.3.5) some meteorite group description will refer to specific minerals found in these meteorites. These minerals are listed in Table 1.2.

Table 1.2 - Common minerals found in meteorites and their chemical formulae.

Mineral Name	Chemical Formula
Enstatite	MgSiO ₃
Olivine	(Mg ⁺² , Fe ⁺²) ₂ SiO ₄ .
Kamacite	α-(Fe,Ni); FeO ^{+0.9} Ni _{0.1}
Taenite	γ-(Fe,Ni)
Troilite	FeS
Schreibersite	(Fe, Ni) ₃ P

1.3.3 Chondrites

Chondritic meteorites are the most commonly found meteorites, with over 27,000 specimens collected, representing ~86% of all finds (Grady, 2000). The chondrites are among the most primitive solar system (Weisberg et al., 2006). All chondrites have Solar-like chemical compositions, minus H and He (Anders and Grevesse 1989). The chondrites are composed of submillimeter- to centimeter-sized components, including chondrules, Ca-Al-rich inclusions (CAIs), amoeboid olivine aggregates (AOAs), Fe,Ni-metal, and fine-grained (< 5 μm) silicate-rich matrix (Fig.1.11). These components formed independently in the protoplanetary disk (e.g. Fedkin and Grossman, 2006) and thus preserve records of the physical and chemical properties of

Figure 1.11 - backscattered electron image of the RBT 04133,8 thin section. Type I chondrules (e.g., Ch3, 5, 6, and 7) appear darker than type II chondrules (e.g., Ch1 and 4) as a result of their lower FeO-contents. Matrix appears bright, like type II chondrules, consistent with the fayalitic compositions of matrix olivine.

the regions where they formed (Weisberg et al., 2006).

The term “chondritic” refers to the presence of chondrules (Morris, 2009). The number of chondrules in a meteorite varies by group and may constitute up to 80% of the volume in the most primitive meteorites (Zanda, 2004). Chondrules typically have mafic (iron- and magnesium-rich silicate) composition and are thought to have formed as molten droplets during transient heating event(s) in the solar nebula (Weisberg et al., 2006).

Chondrites can be split into 3 classes, *carbonaceous*, *ordinary* and *enstatite*:

Ordinary (O) chondrites are comprised of 3 groups (H, L, LL) based on their iron content

(high, low, and low-iron, low-metal, respectively). There are ~14,500 known O chondrites of which 48.8% are H-type, 43.6% are L-type and 7.3% are LL-type (Grady, 2000)

Carbonaceous (C) chondrites contains 8 groups (CI, CM, CO, CV, CK, CR, CH, CB) and constitutes ~4% of recovered samples (Grady, 2000). The composition of CI chondrite most closely resembles our best estimates of solar composition (Anders and Grevesse, 1989).

Enstatite (E) chondrites are characterized in by an abundance of nearly FeO-free mineral enstatite (Macke et al., 2010). E chondrites are split into 2 groups, EH and EL, for high-Fe and low-Fe, respectively (Sears et al., 1982). The enstatite chondrites constitute ~2% of recovered samples (Grady, 2000).

An additional two chondritic meteorite types, R (Rumurutti-like) and K (Kakangari-like), have not yet been linked to a higher order class (Weisburg et al., 2006). The R chondrites are a rare group of meteorites, representing ~0.1% of falls (Bischoff, 2001). They are compositionally similar to the ordinary chondrites but differ in oxygen isotope compositions, which suggests that they may have originated from a different parent body (Ostrogorsky and Dementieva, 2012). The K chondrites are a grouplet of only three chondrites

that share properties with C E and O chondrites but do not fall within any one of the groups entirely. They have oxygen isotopes similar to C chondrites, highly reduced mineral compositions and high metal abundance (similar to E chondrites) and concentrations of refractory elements like O chondrites (Weisberg et al., 1996).

1.3.4 Achondrites

Achondrite is the name given to the category of all meteorites that do not contain chondrules and includes meteorites from asteroids, Mars and the Moon. The achondrites are be split into the primitive achondrites and differentiated achondrites, reflecting a history with no melting in the former and substantial melting in the latter. In this subsection I discuss all achondrites except the irons. Irons form a major part of this thesis (Chapter 4) and require an introductory subsection of their own (1.3.3).

1.3.4.1 Primitive Achondrites

Primitive Achondrites are undifferentiated meteorites containing $\leq 1\%$ reduced metal and do not contain chondrules. The content of non-volatile elements in achondrites is very similar to

that of the chondritic meteorites and thus also similar to solar abundances.

The primitive achondrites are comprised of the ureilite, brachinite, acapulcoite-lodranite and winonaite groups. The iron IAB and IIICD groups contain silicate inclusions with mineralogy and O isotope abundance similar to the Winonaites (e.g. Kracher, 1982) and are therefore part of the primitive achondrites. I will address other iron meteorites in more detail in Section 1.3.3.

1.3.4.2 Differentiated Achondrites

Differentiated achondrites include stony achondrites, stony-irons and the irons (Section 1.3.3).

Stony Achondrites are metal-poor and are comprised of the angrite, aubrite, Lunar and Mars groups, and the Howardites-Eucrites-Diogenites (HED) clan (Weisberg et al., 2006).

The stony irons (*mesosiderites* and *pallasites*) are differentiated meteorites and have roughly equal amounts of metals and silicates. Despite all stony-irons having around 50% silicate and 50% metal, the name does not impose any further relationship between the 2 subgroups. and is no longer as commonly used. Pallasites and mesosiderites are vastly different in both major

Figure 1.12 - a PMG (top) and the Bera Mesosiderite (bottom)

element composition and oxidation state. Their structures are also recognizably different (Figure 1.12).

Mesosiderites have fine-grained metal in a silicate matrix with occasional cm-sized nodules (Figure 1.12, bottom). Conversely, the pallasites are composed of a metallic matrix of kamacite and taenite with olivine inclusions, as well as troilite, schreibersite and several other characteristic minor minerals are also present (Wasson and Choi, 2003). Most (79%) olivine in pallasites comes in either an angular form, the rest

is rounded (Scott 1977b). Olivine inclusions have typical median diameter $[= (\text{length} \times \text{width})^{1/2}]$ greater than 4mm. 79% of recovered pallasites have the angular form of olivine.

“Pallasite” is structural classification (Figure 1.12, top) and does not imply any genetic relationship. Pallasites are widely thought to be samples of the interface between the differentiated iron cores of planetesimals and their silicate crust. Supporting this view, Wasson and Choi (2002) outlines the chemical and structural similarities between PMGs and IIE group iron meteorites.

1.3.5 The Iron Meteorites

The bulk composition of the iron meteorites consists of Fe-Ni in the form of taenite and kamacite. The range of Ni value, spans 5-60% by mass.

The iron meteorites are believed to have formed in the molten metallic cores of planetesimals. Once thought to represent a homogeneous group with a common history, 86% of iron meteorites can now be classified into one of 12 genetic groups, with the remaining 14% of specimens marked “anomalous” (e.g. Malvin et al., 1984). The largest groups, I, IIA, IIIA, IIIB and IVA contain 75% of iron meteorites.

Ten of these 13 groups are considered to be *magmatic* meteorites, as their trace-element fractionation is best modeled by fractional crystallization of a metallic magma (Pernicka and Wasson, 1987). The remaining 2 groups (IAB, III CD) do not fit *magmatic* models.

Irons were initially classified by their structure alone (Brezina, 1885). ‘Structure’ refers to the pattern visible when a polished iron meteorite surface is etched in acid. The majority of iron meteorites show an octahedral (“Widmanstätten”) structure in which kamacite bands (α -Fe,Ni) are arranged within a lattice of taenite (γ -Fe,Ni) (Figure 1.13; Scott and Wasson, 1975). Octahedrite structural groups are defined by the width of kamacite bands within the pattern (Table 1.4, Goldstein and Axon, 1973). While this parameter has remained a useful one, increasing samples and overlapping of groups necessitated additional parameters for classification.

Iron meteorites are now understood to be too complex to classify using a single parameter and often require three independent parameters. Wasson and Scott (1975) describe the most useful taxonomic parameters for grouping the iron meteorites as: (1) chemical class, (2) structural class and (3) kamacite bandwidth.

Figure 1.13 - Plots of (a) Ni vs. Ge and (b) Ni vs. Ir showing the fields for the 13 iron meteorite groups (Scott and Wasson, 1975)

1.3.3.1 Chemical Class (Elemental Abundance)

Goldberg et al. (1951) first describes the grouping (“quantization”) of gallium (Ga)

concentrations in iron meteorites. Further studies revealed similar quantizations in the germanium (Ge) concentrations (Lovering et al., 1957). Ga and Ge are always positively correlated within a group but have both positive and negative correlations with Ni across different groups (Scott and Wasson, 1975).

However, Ga and Ge concentrations alone cannot fully resolve all meteorites into groups. Plots of Ga-Ni and Ge-Ni are more useful for sorting meteorites. Genetic groups and their element ratios (Ga vs. Ni, Ir vs. Ni) are shown graphically in Figure 1.13. Some groups (IIC, IAB) require additional parameters. IIC and IAB overlap on Ga-Ni and Ge-Ni plots but are clearly separated in kamacite bandwidth.

Scott and Wasson (1975) analyzed 479 iron meteorites and reported their iridium (Ir) concentration. In Ni-Ir space (Figure 1.13, bottom), there are clear differences between these relationships and those of Ge-Ni (Figure 1.13, top). Iridium and nickel are negatively correlated, making stripes in the Ni-Ir space that define the groups. The concentration of iridium in groups IIAB and IIIAB spans over 3 orders of magnitude.

Trace element data strongly supports the hypothesis that Ga-Ni and Ge-Ni groups have a common origin. The inter-element correlations

provide a means to sequence meteorites within a group. Kracher et al. (1972) examines data for 6 additional trace elements within group IIF irons (Co, Cu, As, W, Re, Au) and provides log plots of Ni-element for each (Figure insert reference). These clearly show a variety of positive and negative correlations. The trace element composition of iron meteorites is often normalized to the composition of CI chondrites as they have solar abundances.

1.3.3.2 Structural Class

The “structure” of an iron meteorite refers to the arrangement of the kamacite bands within a taenite lattice (Figure 1.14). Kamacite is a mineral found on Earth only in meteorites. That is, it is a meteorite mineral. The unique arrangement The structure is revealed when the polished surface of a meteorite is etched in acid.

All iron meteorites fall into one of 3 structural types: (1) octahedrites, (2) hexahedrites or (3) ataxites. The octahedrites are most common type and their octahedral pattern is known as the Widmanstätten pattern (Figure 1.14). Studies of this structure have been instrumental in understanding the thermal history of metallic meteorites.

Figure 1.14 - microscopic (top) and macroscopic (bottom) Widmanstätten pattern in octahedrites.

1.3.3.3 Kamacite Bandwidths

Octahedrites are split into sub-classes based on their kamacite bandwidths (Table 1.2). The fineness or coarseness of a Widmanstätten pattern depends upon the cooling rate of molten iron core of the parent body. Cooling rates vary within iron meteorite groups (e.g. from 56-338 °C/Myr for the IIIAB) and range from 1.0-17,000 °C/Myr across all groups (Goldstein et al., 2006). An iron meteorite with a given amount of Ni that

cools faster than another meteorite of the same composition will have finer kamacite bands due to the shorter growth time available (Goldstein and Short, 1966). The width of the kamacite bands varies over 3 orders of magnitude, from 0.01mm to 10mm (Figure 1.14), leading to the classification in Table 1.3. Each class of iron meteorite kamacite bandwidths span a factor of ~3. Some bandwidth ranges overlap between groups but this parameter is general useful for resolving chemical groups.

Table 1.3 Kamacite bandwidth and cooling rate variations within the Octahedrite structural class (Goldstein and Short, 1967).

Texture	Symbol	Kamacite Bandwidth	Cooling rate (°C/Myr)
Coarsest	Ogg	> 3.3 mm	0.8 - 6
Coarse	Og	1.3 - 3.3 mm	0.8 - 12
Medium	Om	0.5 - 1.3 mm	0.4 - 25
Fine	Of	0.2 - 0.5 mm	0.4 - 100
Finest	Off	< 0.2 mm	0.4 - 500

1.4 Goals of This Study

In this study I explore the constraints that the study of asteroid and meteorite compositions impose on the formation of our Solar System. I also explore how asteroid and meteorite compositions inform impact hazard assessment and how they can be applied to space-based commercial pursuits.

In Chapter 2 I investigate the known links between meteorites and asteroids by analyzing 18 reflection spectra of Near Earth Asteroids (NEAs) and 3 Main Belt asteroids taken with FLWO 1.5-meter-FAST optical spectrograph at 0.55-0.90 μm wavelengths.

In Chapter 3 I present a database of *meteorite minerals* that I compiled. *Meteorite minerals* are exotic materials found only in meteorites.

In Chapter 4 I present a database of elemental abundances iron meteorites that I compiled. I will then explore genetic relationships between different groups of meteorites.

Finally, in Chapter 5 I explore an asteroid mining application of the database presented in Chapter 4. I perform basic statistical analysis of the relationship between “observable” (by a proximity measurement) elements that can serve as proxies for the, much harder to observe, valuable trace elements.

2. Spectral Classification of Near-Earth Asteroids

Here we present the visible ($\sim 0.55 - 0.90 \mu\text{m}$) reflectance spectra of 18 near-Earth asteroids (NEAs), of which 7 have not previously been classified, and 3 Main Belt asteroids. The studied NEAs are: 2000 UV13, 1998 WT24, 2003 NZ6, 2002 UR3, 2007 BG29, 1994 AW1, 2004 MQ1, 1924 TD, 1950 KA, 1929 SH, 1948 OA, 1971 FA, 1950 LA, 1959 LM, 1999 JD6, 1999 JV6, 2002 QE15 and 2003 SD220. The studied Main Belt asteroids are: 16 Psych, 27 Euterpe and 230 Athamantis. The observations were conducted with the 1.5-meter+FAST spectrograph at Mt Hopkins, Arizona. Based on preliminary attempts at classification with the M4AST system (based on DeMeo et al., 2014). Recommendations for their classification are offered.

2.1 Introduction

The use of charge-coupled device (CCD) spectroscopy for asteroids was first implemented by Vilas and Smith (1985) and for near-Earth asteroids (NEAs) by Luu and Jewitt (1990). It has since played a crucial role in the development of asteroid reflectance properties analysis. High signal-to-noise ($> 20/\text{resolution element}$), low-to-moderate resolution ($R \sim 300$) spectra are now routinely obtained for faint asteroids (e.g. Bus and Binzel, 2002; Michelsen et al., 2006).

There are at least 135 mineralogically distinct meteorites types (Meibom and Clark, 1999) that originate in the fragmentation of

primitive and differentiated asteroids in the Main Belt (Michelsen et al., 2005). However, the links between asteroids and meteorites are poorly defined (Bell et al., 1989; Cellino, 2000). Asteroid reflectance spectra provide clues to these links.

Several systems of classification have been developed for the classification of asteroid reflectance spectra into taxonomic groups (e.g. Tholen, 1998; Bus and Binzel, 2002; DeMeo et al., 2009). These classification systems are based on principal component analysis (PCA) of asteroid reflectance spectra.

The NEA population is particularly interesting because it informs the history of the

Solar System by giving us access to the dominant, by number, *sub-kilometer asteroid population*, which are unobservable in the Main Belt. NEA compositions provide, statistically, their original locations in the Main Belt (DeMeo and Carry 2014), and the numbers of each type test dynamical models (e.g. Bottke et al. 2001, Greenstreet and Gladman 2013).

The number of known NEAs is now growing at a pace of ~ 1500 objects/year (Galache et al., 2015). However, we know rather little about the great majority of NEAs. Sizes depend on an assumed albedo, which can range from a few percent for carbonaceous asteroids, to several tens of percent for Vestas and metallic asteroids (e.g. Cellino et al., 1989; Harris and Drube, 2014). Despite an abundance of known NEAs, there is not such an abundance of classified spectra. Only 10% of discovered NEAs are being spectrally classified (Michelsen et al., 2005).

Thermal infrared ($>3 \mu\text{m}$) measurements can give improved sizes, based on their black body emission. The NEOWISE-R project is the near-Earth object survey continuation of the Wide-field Infrared Survey Explorer (WISE) mission. WISE surveyed the sky in 3.4, 4.6, 12, and 22 μm wavelengths (Wright et al., 2010). NEOWISE-R uses the two shorter wavelength

bands to identify and measure their thermal sizes (to $\pm 25\%$) and albedo of asteroids, and comets (Mainzer et al. 2014). NEOWISE began in December 2009, reactivating the WISE spacecraft, and will be in operation until early-2017 when WISE will become uncontrollable.

Main Belt asteroids show correlations of albedo with spectral type (Hong et al., 2016). NEOWISE gives us a chance to obtain spectral types for sub-kilometer asteroids to extend these correlations.

Here we present the visible-wavelength spectra for 22 previously known NEAs with $V < 17$ that were observed by NEOWISE-R, some with already known spectral types. I describe the observations and the data reduction procedures. I then use the M4AST online tool to perform chi-squared fits to the average spectra from the DeMeo et al. (2014) spectral taxonomy and assign preliminary spectral classes to the observed NEAs. The results for the asteroids previously classified provide a measure of the reliability of our FAST observations.

2.2 Instrumentation

Observations were made with the 1.5-m Tillinghast reflector telescope, located on Mt Hopkins in Tucson, AZ. The 1.5-m telescope is equipped with the FAST spectrograph¹¹. We used a 300 lines mm⁻¹ grating blazed at 4750 Å, giving a resolution of 6 Å and a resolving power of ~792.

The Tillinghast CCD is FAST3, a UA STA520A 2688 x 512 pixel CCD with a pixel size of 15 μm (Fabricant et al., 1998). This corresponds to 1.21"/pixel.

The FAST optics are primarily reflective and are adequately sized to prevent vignetting, and use high-performance coatings (Fabricant et al., 1998). The high measured system peak efficiency of 26% (fraction of light incident on the primary detected at the CCD) demonstrates that the throughput of reflective optics can be quite competitive with that of refractive optics (Fabricant et al., 1998). This high throughput allows us to take spectra of V=17.0 objects. The Tillinghast can reliably track moving targets up to 900"/min (sidereal rate) using linear RA and dec. tracking rates.

¹¹ <http://tdc-www.harvard.edu/instruments/fast/>

¹² www.minorplanetcenter.net/iau/MPEph/MPEph.html

2.3 Observations

We obtained moderate-resolution reflection spectra of 22 near-Earth asteroids. Targets were taken from the bi-weekly lists provided by the NEOWISE-R project. NEOWISE-R detects a mean of five V<17 NEAs per month, with an FLWO accessible dec. >-30. Therefore there are ~20 NEOWISE-detected NEAs per trimester observable from FLWO.

The Minor Planter Center Ephemerides Service¹² provides the nightly RA, Dec, sky motion and V of each target. Each asteroid was observed on a single night near its brightest magnitude on this apparition. The V magnitude of each observation is provided in Table 2.4 and summarized in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.1 - Histogram of V magnitudes for FAST NEA observations. Observations were made over 14 nights from May 2015 to February 2016.

Table 2.1 - FLWO/FAST Observations of NEAs (Program 223)

Asteroid	UT date	Exp. Time (s)	Airmass	V	H	Solar Analog
2015B						
J9800H 1998 KH	2015/05/11	1200	2.05	17.6	16.3	HD134664
J9800H 1998 KH	2015/05/11	1200	2.06			
J9800H 1998 KH	2015/05/11	1200	2.10			
1580 Betulia	2015/05/11	900	1.35	14.7	14.5	HIP56948
1580 Betulia	2015/05/11	900	1.36			
1580 Betulia	2015/05/11	900	1.38			
1580 Betulia	2015/05/17	900	1.23			BS4486
1580 Betulia	2015/05/17	900	1.25			
1580 Betulia	2015/05/17	900	1.28			
1627 Ivar	2015/06/14	1200	1.93	17.1	13.2	HD86728
1627 Ivar	2015/06/14	1200	2.23			
5186 1994 AW1	2015/07/15	720	1.77	14.2	17.6	HD117860
5186 1994 AW1	2015/07/15	720	1.82			
5186 1994 AW1	2015/07/15	202	1.85			
1036 Ganymed	2015/07/15	300	1.26	13.3	9.5	HD138573
1036 Ganymed	2015/07/15	300	1.29			
1036 Ganymed	2015/07/15	300	1.30			
1036 Ganymed	2015/07/15	300	1.32			
242191 2003 NZ6	2015/07/15	1200	1.24	16.8	19	HD144873
242191 2003 NZ6	2015/07/15	1200	1.30			
242191 2003 NZ6	2015/07/15	1200	1.37			
242191 2003 NZ6	2015/07/15	1200	1.44			
85989 1999 JD6	2015/07/15	420	1.14	13.8	17.1	HIP73815
85989 1999 JD6	2015/07/15	420	1.12			
85989 1999 JD6	2015/07/15	420	1.11			
85989 1999 JD6	2015/07/15	420	1.09			
4183 Cuno	2015/07/15	1200	1.49	17	14.4	HD219018
4183 Cuno	2015/07/15	1200	1.44			
4183 Cuno	2015/07/15	1200	1.42			
4183 Cuno	2015/07/15	1200	1.40			
2015C						
68216 2001 CV26	2015/10/11	1200	3.44	17	16.4	N/A
1980 Tezcatlipoca	2015/10/12	900	1.15	15.4	13.9	Hiltner 600
2002 QE15	2015/10/12	1500	1.05	16.9	16.2	Hiltner 600
163899 2003 SD220	2015/11/07	900	1.24	15.8	16.9	HD89010
163899 2003 SD220	2015/11/07	900	1.20			
163899 2003 SD220	2015/11/07	900	1.16			
27 Euterpe	2015/11/07	180	1.07	10	7	HD89010
16 Psyche	2015/11/07	180	1.26	10	5.9	HD89010
230 Athamantis	2015/11/07	360	1.23	10.7	7.4	HD89010
33342 1998 WT24	2015/11/13	1200	1.48	16.1	17.9	HD78538
33342 1998 WT24	2015/11/13	1200	1.41			
33342 1998 WT24	2015/11/13	1200	1.35			
33342 1998 WT24	2015/12/14	500	1.32	12.1		HD9986
33342 1998 WT24	2015/12/14	500	1.35			
33342 1998 WT24	2015/12/14	500	1.39			
16 Psyche	2015/12/14	180	1.03	9.5	5.9	Hyades 142
230 Athamantis	2015/12/14	240	1.03	10.0	7.4	Hyades 142
345722 2007 BG29	2015/12/14	1200	1.41	16.8	18	HD129357
345722 2007 BG29	2015/12/14	1200	1.36			
345722 2007 BG29	2015/12/14	1200	1.31			
1864 Daedalus	2015/12/15	1200	1.34	15.4	14.5	HD186408

Asteroid	UT date	Exp. Time (s)	Airmass	V	H	Solar Analog
1864 Daedalus	2015/12/15	1200	1.39			
1864 Daedalus	2015/12/15	1200	1.46			
253106 2002 UR3	2015/12/15	1800	1.42	16.8	16.4	HD1835
253106 2002 UR3	2015/12/15	1800	1.61			
253106 2002 UR3	2015/12/15	1800	1.89			
33342 1998WT24	2015/12/15	500	1.15	16.1	17.9	HD19445
33342 1998WT24	2015/12/15	500	1.16			
33342 1998WT24	2015/12/15	500	1.18			
2016A/January						
85990 1999 JV6	2016/01/10	720	1.34	14.6	20.1	HD81809
85990 1999 JV6	2016/01/10	720	1.36			
85990 1999 JV6	2016/01/10	720	1.38			
85990 1999 JV6	2016/01/10	720	1.40			
2004 MQ1	2016/01/11	1800	1.38	16.6	18	BDp174708
2004 MQ1	2016/01/11	1800	1.41			
2004 MQ1	2016/01/11	1800	1.44			
1685 Toro	2016/02/02	300	1.30	13.0		HD29461
2000 UV13	2016/02/02	1800	1.46	15.5		HD29461

For each asteroid, 2 - 4 spectral images were usually taken in a single night. To detect the low contrast features, we need to achieve a S/N of 30, thus we have exposures ranging from 60 to 1200 seconds for the faintest objects. Where possible objects were observed with minimum airmass.

To determine the relative reflectance of the asteroid, following standard asteroid observing procedures, Solar analog stars were observed each observing night at similar air masses as the asteroids. Flat fields, bias and arc line spectra were acquired each night. An observing log for all of the asteroids and solar analogs presented in Table 2.1.

Of the observed NEAs, two (1998 KH and 2001 CV₂₆) were excluded from our dataset.

1998 KH was only observed in the wavelength range from $\sim 3500-7500 \text{ \AA}$, making it incompatible with the rest of our data and with our classification method. 2001 CV₂₆ had an airmass of 3.44 and the only solar analog observed on that night had an airmass of 1.48. Observing was terminated thereafter. We also note that the asteroids 16 Psyche, 27 Euterpe and 230 Athamantis are Main Belt asteroids. We use these Main Belt asteroids as we use the already-classified NEAs, to assess the accuracy of our classification method.

2.4 Data reduction

The procedures for the reduction and calibration of asteroid CCD spectra were first outlined by Vilas and Smith (1985). The processes

Figure 2.2 - Four steps in the reduction of asteroid spectra. (a) Two-dimensional bias and flat-field corrected spectral image of 1998 WT24, taken on December 14, 2015. (b) Extracted one-dimensional spectrum obtained by summing the raw counts (ADUs) along each column within the extraction aperture. (c) Spectrum for 1998 WT24 and the solar-analog star HD9986 after the wavelength solution has been applied and the spectra have been normalized to 1.0 at 6000 Å for simplicity. (d) Ratio spectrum (1998 WT24 divided by solar analog), normalized at 6000 Å. The noise increases towards the red end of the spectrum, partly due to fringing.

may vary depending on the instrumentation and observing strategies used by each observing program, however the fundamental steps used to reduce asteroid spectra remain the same.

The FAST data was been pre-processed in a standard way by the Telescope Data Center at SAO using the software package RoadRunner, an automated reduction system for long slit

spectroscopic data (Tokarz and Roll, 1997). The RoadRunner package takes the raw two-dimensional spectral data (Figure 2.2 (a)) and performs bias and flat-fielding corrections, using calibration images taken nightly at the telescope. It then extracts a one-dimensional spectrum (Figure 2.2 (b)) and applies a wavelength calibration using a dispersion model based on

measured lines in the Hg–Ar–Xe calibration lamp images. When this correction was applied, the pixels making up the 1-D spectra were uniformly re-binned to a dispersion of 1.48 Å, allowing different spectra to be easily compared and combined. We did not apply a correction for atmospheric extinction to the data.

Using the Image Reduction and Analysis Facility (IRAF), I then reduce the data to a uniform, normalized reflection form for classification according to the following steps:

1. Combine each of the one-dimensional, wavelength-calibrated asteroid spectra using the *scombine* task in IRAF to form an average spectrum for each target.
2. Combine each of the one-dimensional, wavelength-calibrated solar analog spectra, also using *scombine*.
3. Divide each combined asteroid spectrum by a combined solar analog spectrum from the same night at similar air mass (within ± 0.15) using the IRAF function *sarith*.

4. Smooth the ratioed data by reassigning each reflectance value by the mean of the 100 preceding values.
5. Normalize the ratioed, smoothed asteroid spectrum to unity at 6000 Å to facilitate the comparison of spectra for different objects¹³.
6. Trim the data from 5650 to 9000 Å to produce a uniform data set, independent of the detector used, the brightness of the asteroid, or the conditions in which the observations were made.

The resulting NEA normalized reflection spectra are shown in Figure 2.3.

2.5 Asteroid Classification

We used the M4AST online classification tool¹⁴ (Popescu et al., 2012) to classify our spectra. M4AST takes spectra in the form of list of (wavelength, relative reflectance) points. It then parameterizes the spectra at intervals of 500 Å. The spectra were uploaded to the temporary database and classified with the “chi squared” and

¹³ It is standard to normalize at 0.55 μm (e.g. DeMeo et al., 2009) however our data did not uniformly extend sufficiently far to the blue.

¹⁴ <http://m4ast.imcce.fr/m4ast/>

Figure 2.3 - Reduced and normalized FAST reflection spectra. Top: previously classified asteroids, comprised of 11 NEAs and 3 Main Belt asteroids. Bottom: NEAs that have not been previously classified.

Figure 2.3 - M4AST χ^2 -produced fits to FAST spectra of asteroids with known classification. The observation data was loaded into the temporary database and binned every 0.5 μm (shown as a red line with stars) The best fit, as determined by M4AST is given by the dark blue line, the next best fit is represented by the light green line and the third best fit is represented by the light blue line.

“DeMeo taxonomy” options selected. The Results of this classification are presented in Figure 2.4.

The output is a plot of the parameterized version of the spectrum being classified and the three best spectral fits. Spectral fits are calculated using the least squares fitting method on the average spectra from the DeMeo taxonomy.

There are two major limitations of the M4AST classification tool; (1) it parameterizes the data coarsely (6 points across 3000 Å) and (2)

only the DeMeo taxonomy (0.45-2.45 μm) is available for fitting our visible wavelength spectra. With a larger number of points, the tool would better sample our spectra and avoid losing (or over-emphasizing, in the case of 2004 MQ1) certain features.

2.6 Discussion

Figure 2.2 provides all the reflectance spectra obtained. The top panel of Figure 2.2 is

Table 2.1 - FLWO/FAST/M4AST classifications of 21 NEAs and 3 Main Belt asteroids

Number	Name	Provisional Designation	This work			Previous work	Reference	
			Slope	Class. 1 (grade)	Class. 2 (grade)	Class. 3 (grade)		Classification
20826		2000 UV ₁₃		Sr (1)	Sq (2)	K (3)		
33342		1998 WT ₂₄		Xc (1)	X (1)	Xe (2)		
68216		2001 CV ₂₆		-	-	-		
152760		1999 KH		-	-	-		
242191		2003 NZ ₆		Cg (2)	C (2)	B (2)		
253106		2002 UR ₃		A (2)	R (3)	Sa (3)		
345722		2007 BG ₂₉		Sr (1)	S (2)	Sa (2)		
385186		1994 AW ₁		D (2)	L (3)	T (3)		
455554		2004 MQ ₁		Xc (2)	Cb (2)	Xk (2)		
1036	Ganymed	1924 TD		S (1)	Sv (2)	L (3)	S	[5]
1580	Betulia	1950 KA		Xk (2)	Cb (1)	Xc (3)	C	[1]
1627	Ivar	1929 SH		L (1)	T (3)	D (3)	S/Sw	[6]
1685	Toro	1948 OA		S (1)	K (2)	Sr (3)	S	[2]
1864	Daedalus	1971 FA		Sq (1)	Sr (2)	K (3)	Sq	[5]
1980	Tezcatlipoca	1950 LA		D (3)	Sv (2)	A (3)	Sw	[5]
4183	Cuno	1959 LM		Sq (2)	K (2)	Xk (3)	Sq	[7]
85989		1999 JD ₆		T (1)	D (3)	X (2)	K	[4]
85990		1999 JV ₆		X (1)	Xc (2)	Xe (3)	Xk	[4]
142040		2002 QE ₁₅		Sv (2)	A (3)	D (3)	Sv	[3]
163899		2003 SD ₂₂₀		K (1)	Xe (3)	Xk (3)	S/Sr	[8]
16	Psyche	-		Cb (1)	Xk (2)	Xc (2)	Xk	[5]
27	Euterpe	1945 KB		K (1)	Xe (3)	S (2)	S	[5]
230	Athamantis	1949 WG		Sq (1)	Sr (2)	K (3)	Sl	[2]

References: [1] Tedesco et al., 1978, [2] Bus, 1999, [3] Michelsen et al., 2005, [4] Binzel et al., 2001, [5] DeMeo et al., 2009, [6] Sanchez et al., 2012, [7] Popescu et al., 2014, [8] DeMeo et al., 2014

populated with the reflectance spectra of asteroids that have already been taxonomic classified. These spectra serve as test of the quality of our observations and classification technique. We compare the spectral fits obtained with the M4AST tool to the previously determined spectral type(s) for each asteroid. In 7 of 14 cases, one of the 3 M4AST spectral fits agreed with the spectral type determined by other studies. In 11 cases M4AST suggested a spectral type that was in the same spectral complex as the classification from other studies. For example, M4AST classifies 1999 JV6 as X, Xc and Xe while Binzel et al. (2001) classifies the same asteroid as an Xk-type. In this instance, M4AST determined that 1999 JV6 is an X-complex asteroid but did not identify the sub-type. These results are provided in Table 2.1.

The bottom half of Figure 2.2 is populated with NEAs that have not previously been classified. Amongst these spectra, two (2000 UV₁₅, 2007 BG₂₉) have a peak turn down at ~7500 Å which is characteristic of S-complex asteroids. 2003 NZ3 appears to have a neutral slope with a potential absorption feature at ~8500 Å. 1998 WT24 is relatively featureless with a neutral to low slope. 1994 AW1 is similarly without absorption features but has a steeper red

slope. 2004 MQ1 and 2002 UR3 have irregular, poor quality spectra and would benefit from being observed again.

Given that M4AST has some serious limitations, I have implemented a grading system for the quality of its classifications based on a “chi-by-eye” assessment of the fits. Only M4AST-suggested classifications rated 1 or 2 will be considered to be the true taxonomic class of the NEAs.

Table 2.2 - M4AST classification grading scheme

Grade	Definition	N
1	Near-perfect match	15
2	Not perfect but not too far off	25
3	Unlikely to be correct classification	22
		63

The grades assigned to each of the M4AST classifications are listed in Table 2.1. Using this classification grading scheme, the new NEAs have been classified only by the higher level complex,. These are listed in Table 2.3.

Table 2.3 - Preliminary classification of 7 new NEAs

NEA	Complex	H mag
(20826) 2000 UV ₁₃	S	13.8
(33342) 1998 WT ₂₄	X	17.9
(242191) 2003 NZ ₆	C or B	19.0
(253106) 2002 UR ₃	A	16.6
(345722) 2007 BG ₂₉	S	18.1
(385186) 1994 AW ₁	D	17.7
(455554) 2004 MQ ₁	X or C	18.1

2.7 Conclusions and Future Work

We have presented visible spectra and preliminary classifications for 7 near-Earth asteroids. We used the M4AST online classification tool and chi-by-eye evaluations to determine the fit of our spectra to the proposed models. Our classifications would be improved with a less coarse parameterization of data for model fitting.

Next steps:

1. Compare spectral type with NEOWISE-R sizes and albedos
2. Get more new NEAs up through early-2017, when WISE will no longer be operable.
3. Extend albedo/type correlations to smaller sizes.

3. Meteorite Minerals: A Database

Dozens of exotic materials are found only in meteorites. These “meteorite minerals” are formed in the Solar System’s proto-planetary disk, in the interiors of planetesimals, and in high-speed collisions. Motivated by a small collection of paper titles containing the phrase “a new meteorite mineral”, we set out to identify a complete list of known meteorite minerals and create a database containing their identifying chemical, physical and optical properties. A literature review was performed and a uniform database containing 66 meteorite minerals was compiled, of which 14 were later found to occur on Earth and 20 were later synthesized. The database is stored in excel format and will be available at the online in early June. We encourage contributions to this database and hope that it will highlight gaps within the current literature.

3.1 Introduction

The early Solar System explored a wider range of formation conditions than occur on Earth. The cold ($\sim 10\text{K}$) regions of the Solar nebula in the slowly cooling cores of planetesimals (Myr – Gyr), and the high speed ($\sim 25\text{ km s}^{-1}$) collisions of planetesimals and their derivatives, are all conditions that contributed to the formation of the vast and array of minerals we have available to us in the Solar System today.

In materials physics, first-principles total-energy calculations for compounds of a given stoichiometry have identified metastable, or even

stable, structures distinct from known structures obtained by synthesis under laboratory conditions (Rittenhouse & Sadeghpour, 2010; Huang et al., 2013).

Meteorite/asteroid/comet samples may then be expected to contain novel structures that could suggest new classes of materials for first-principles and laboratory investigation. The result of these unusual environments is that meteorites contain significant numbers of minerals not found naturally occurring on Earth. These are often called ‘meteorite minerals’. These novel minerals give us clues to the conditions at their formation

and so to Solar System history. Some of the meteorite minerals have unusual properties important for materials science, e.g. hardness greater than diamond, though these are little explored yet.

The existence of meteorite minerals is well-known but the literature describing these minerals is widely dispersed and inconsistent in nature. Furthermore, there is not a database dedicated to meteorite minerals and meteorite minerals are rarely mentioned explicitly in more

general meteorite databases. Here we present a compilation of data on 66 meteorite minerals to make them more accessible to a wider range of researchers. An online database is also available.

3.2 Data Aggregation

We searched the scientific literature for reports of meteorite minerals. Initial key term searches were conducted on the Harvard University HOLLIS database. Key terms included “meteorite,” “new mineral,” “discovered” and

Table 3.1 - Meteorite minerals and their chemical formulae. † Found on Earth, * Synthesized in laboratory.

<i>Mineral</i>	<i>Chemical Formula</i>	<i>Mineral</i>	<i>Chemical Formula</i>
Adrianite	Ca ₁₂ (Al ₄ Mg ₃ Si ₇)O ₃₂ Cl ₆	Krinovite	Na ₂ Mg ₄ Cr ₂ [Si ₆ O ₁₈]O ₂
Akimotoite	(Mg,Fe)SiO ₃	Krotite	CaAl ₂ O ₄
Allabogdanite	(Fe,Ni) ₂ P	Lonsdaleite †*	C
Allendite	Sc ₄ Zr ₃ O ₁₂	Majindeite	Mg ₂ Mo ₃ O ₈
Andreyivanovite	FeCrP	Majorite †*	Mg ₃ (MgSi)(SiO ₄) ₃
Barringerite †	(Fe,Ni) ₂ P	Merrhueite *	(K,Na) ₂ (Fe ²⁺ ,Mg) ₅ Si ₁₂ O ₃₀
Brearleyite	Ca ₁₂ Al ₁₄ O ₃₂ C ₁₂	Merrillite *	Ca ₉ NaMg(PO ₄) ₇
Brezinaite	Cr ₃ S ₄	Moissanite †*	SiC
Brianite	Na ₂ CaMg(PO ₄) ₂	Moniptite	MoNiP
Browneite *	MnS	Murchisite *	Cr ₅ S ₆
Buchwaldite *	NaCaPO ₄	Nierite *	Si ₃ N ₄
Burnettite	CaVAISI ₆ O ₆	Niningerite	MnS
Buseckite	(Fe,Zn,Mn)S	Nuwaite *	Ni ₆ (Ge,Sn)(S,Te) ₂
Carlsbergite	CrN	Oldhamite *	(Ca,Mg)S
Chukanovite	Fe ₂ (CO ₃)(OH) ₂	Osbornite *	TiNi
Cohenite †	(Fe,Ni,Co) ₃ C	Panethite *	(Na,Ca) ₂ (Mg,Fe) ₂ (PO ₄) ₂
Davisite *	CaScAlSiO ₆	Panguite	(Ti ⁴⁺ ,Sc,Al,Mg,Zr,Ca) _{1.8} O ₃
Daubréelite	(Fe ²⁺)(Cr ³⁺) ₂ S ₄	Paquite	Ca ₃ TiSi ₂ (Al ₂ Ti)O ₁₄
Dmitryivanovite	CaAl ₂ O ₄	Ringwoodite †	Mg ₂ SiO ₄
Droninoite	Ni ₃ Fe ³⁺ Cl(OH) ₈ ·2H ₂ O	Roaldite	(Fe,Ni) ₄ N
Farringtonite	Mg ₃ (PO ₄) ₂	Rudashevskyite	(Fe,Zn)S
Florenskyite *	FeTiP	Schreibersite †*	(Fe, Ni) ₃ P
Grossite †*	CaAl ₄ O ₇	Sinoite	Si ₂ N ₂ O
Grossmanite	CaTi ³⁺ AlSiO ₆	Stanfieldite	Ca ₄ (Mg,Fe ²⁺ ,Mn ²⁺) ₅ (PO ₄) ₆
Hapkeite	Fe ₂ Si	Steinhardtite	α-Fe: Al _{0.38} Ni _{0.32} Fe _{0.30}
Haxonite	(Fe,Ni) ₂₃ C ₆	Taenite †	γ-(Fe,Ni)
Heideite	(Fe,Cr) ^{1+x} (Ti,Fe) ₂ S ₄ , x=0.15	Tetrataenite †*	FeNi
Hexamolybdenum	(Mo,Ru,Fe,Ir,Os)	Tistarite	Ti ₂ O ₃
Hibonite-(Fe) †	(Fe,Mg)Al ₁₂ O ₁₉	Troilite †	FeS
Hutcheonite	Ca ₃ Ti ₂ (SiAl ₂)O ₁₂	Ureyite †*	NaCrSi ₂ O ₆
Kamacite	α-(Fe,Ni); FeO ^{+0.9} Ni _{0.1}	Wadsleyite †	β-(Mg,Fe) ₂ SiO ₄
Kangite	(Sc,Ti,Al,Zr,Mg,C) ₂ O ₃	Wassonite *	TiS
Keilite	(Fe,Mn,Mg,Ca,Cr)S	Yagiite	(Na,K) _{1.5} Mg ₂ (Al,Mg) ₃ (Si,Al) ₁₂ O ₃₀

“meteorite mineral.” These searches resulted in an initial list of 31 minerals. Examining citations for each of these papers led to an additional 16 meteorite minerals being identified. An initial table was compiled with these 47 minerals.

Searches were then performed for each of the minerals on online mineralogy databases webmineral.com (last updated 2012) and mindat.org. These databases listed additional occurrences of meteorite minerals that I had not identified during preliminary searches, providing new search terms. This led to the identification of 15 more meteorite minerals.

Table 3.1 presents the list of 66 meteorite minerals and their chemical formulae. Evidently, though this list was compiled with due diligence, it is likely incomplete.

3.3 Database Contents

A database table was constructed with each of the minerals occupying a row and columns representing data on mineral occurrence, crystallographic structure, physical properties and optical properties. The database is currently comprised of 66 minerals that have been approved by the International Mineralogical Association (<http://www.ima-mineralogy.org>).

The most commonly reported data for meteorite mineral discoveries are the 23 entries listed in Table 3.2. For a more detailed description of the terms in Table 3.2 see Appendix B.

Most of the meteorite minerals are found as milligram, micron-sized particles. This makes measuring their physical properties problematic. Due to microscopic crystal sizes, it was common for a number of minerals to have many unmeasured physical properties. Twinning, cleavage, fracture and tenacity were often unreported.

Entries in Table 3.2 marked with an asterisk were less frequently recorded than others. This is in part due to the typically micron-scale size of meteorite minerals, making many of these properties difficult to measure.

Table 3.2 - Properties in database

<i>General</i>	<i>Physical</i>	<i>Optical</i>
Name	Unit cell	Color
Chemical formula	Crystal structure	Streak*
Type Meteorite	Hardness	Lustre
Publication	Density	Diaphaneity
Crystal habit	Cleavage	Optics
Occurrences	Fracture	Refractive index*
	Tenacity*	Pleochroism*
		Birefringence*
		Extinction*
		2V angle*

* Less frequently recorded

3.4 Compilation of Properties

The database has been simplified for presentation here (excluding all asterisked

properties from Table 3.2) and is presented Tables 3.5-3.7. The full version of the database will be accessible as an excel spreadsheet at www.cfa.harvard.edu.

Table 3.5 presents the discovery data: type mineral, the article documenting the mineral discovery, crystal habit and occurrence. Table 3.6 provides crystallographic data: unit cell, crystal structure, hardness, density, cleavage and fracture. Table 3.7 provides optical data: color, lustre, diaphaneity, optics, refractive index and birefringence.

3.5 Declassified Minerals

There are two ways in which a meteorite mineral, first discovered in a meteorite, may be declassified; later discovery on Earth (Section 3.5.1) or later synthesis in the lab (Section 3.5.2). 7 minerals have both been found on Earth and synthesized in the lab.

3.5.1 Later Earth Discoveries

We identified 14 minerals that, though they were first discovered in meteorites, were later found on Earth (Table 3.3). Citations refer to their discovery on Earth.

Table 3.3 - Meteorite minerals discovered on Earth

<i>Mineral</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Citation</i>
Barringerite	China	Keqiao et al., 1983

<i>Mineral</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Citation</i>
Cohenite	Greenland	Lovering, 1964
Grossite	Israel	Weber and Bischoff, 1994
Hibonite	Madagascar	Rakotondrazafy et al., 1996
Lonsdaleite	Burma	Kaminskii et al., 1985
Majorite	Mexico	Israde-Alcántara et al., 2012
Moissanite	Earth's mantle	Collerson et al., 2000
	Bohemia	Bauer et al., 1963
	Aegean Sea	Di Pierro et al., 2003
Ringwoodite	Earth's mantle	Grocholski, 2014
Schreibersite	Greenland	Pauly, 1969
Taenite		
Tetrataenite	India	Nayak and Meyer, 2015
Troilite	Bulgaria	Atanasov, 1990
Ureyite	Burma	Harlow and Olds, 1987
Wadsleyite	Earth's mantle	Takashi et al., 2008

3.5.2 Synthesis of Meteorite Minerals

Since their discovery in meteorites, 20 of the meteorite minerals have been synthesized in laboratories (Table 3.4). However this is not always possible. There have been over fifty unsuccessful attempts to synthesize Krinovite (Olsen and Fuchs, 1968), with no success. Citations refer to papers discussing their synthesis.

Table 3.4 - Meteorite minerals synthesized in lab

<i>Mineral</i>	<i>Citation</i>
Brownite	Skromme et al. 1995; Lu et al. 2001
Buchwaldite	
Davisite	
Florenskyite	
Grossite	Stebbins et al., 2001
Lonsdaleite	Bundy and Kasper, 1967
Majorite	Angel et al., 1989
Merrillite	
Merrihueite	
Moissanite	Saddow and Agarwal, 2004
Murchisite	
Nierite	
Nuwaite	Baranov et al., 2003
Oldhamite	Mason, 1992; Peterson et al., 1999
Osbornite	
Panethite	
Schreibersite	La Cruz, 2015
Tetrataenite	Pauleve et al., 1962; Chamberod et al., 1979; Lima et al., 2003

<i>Mineral</i>	<i>Citation</i>
Ureyite	Frondel and Klein, 1965
Wassonite	

3.6 Discussion

3.6.1 Distribution by meteorite type

The meteorite minerals are broadly distributed across a range of meteorites. Figure 3.1 quantifies the distribution. Excluded from Figure 3.1 are the occurrences of haxonite, kamacite, cohenite, oldhamite and tetrataenite. This is because our plot describes the number of meteorites within each group that contain a meteorite mineral and these minerals are present in a large number of meteorites within one meteorite group. Haxonite is “common” in iron meteorites and carbonaceous chondrites (Scott, 1971). Kamacite, taenite and cohenite are considered to be ubiquitous in iron meteorites (Perry, 1944; Scott 1971).

Oldhamite has been discovered in all enstatite chondrites which have been carefully examined (Mason, 1966). Tetrataenite has been identified in over 50 chondrites and mesosiderites (Clarke and Scott, 1980).

The known occurrences of meteorite minerals are biased by the meteorites that are

Figure 3.1 - (Top) number of distinct occurrences of a meteorite mineral by meteorite type, Allende discoveries highlighted in red. (Bottom) number of distinct occurrences of a meteorite mineral by meteorite type as a fraction of the number of known meteorites in each group.

studied in detail. Allende is the most studied meteorite. 15 meteorite minerals have been discovered in Allende, a CV3 group meteorite, in the past 10 years (Ma, 2015). That these minerals have not been identified elsewhere, could well be due to limited searching. Therefore, Figure 3.1 may not reflect the true occurrence of meteorite minerals. Figure 3.2 provides a more descriptive illustration of the distribution but still suffers from limited searching.

Several minerals that have been synthesized occur in the same meteorite as

Figure 3.2 - Distribution of meteorite minerals across meteorite groups. The meteorite minerals have been organized by mineral group. The “other” category is a collection of minerals that are each from different mineral groups. The key describes the number of meteorites within a meteorite group that a particular meteorite mineral has been found in.

minerals which have not been synthesized. This may be because there have not been attempts to synthesize the other meteorite minerals found in meteorites that contain both synthesized and not-synthesized minerals.

Alternatively, as meteorites each contain several different components (e.g. Hernández-Bernal and Solé, 2010) the components of the meteorite containing the synthesized and unsynthesized meteorite minerals may have formed at different times under different temperature and pressure conditions.

Hernández-Bernal and Solé (2010) reports K-Ar and Pb-Pb ages (see Chapter 1.3.1.2) for individual chondrules from eight chondrites, demonstrating a wide range of ages (e.g. 2.1 - 3.9 Gyr) for chondrules within the same meteorite.

3.6.2 Interesting Meteorite Mineral Properties

Some of the minerals have interesting properties and are listed below:

Lonsdaleite is a hexagonal polymorph of diamond. According to theoretical calculations, it is harder than cubic diamond by 58%, making it the hardest mineral known (Pan et al., 2009). Lonsdaleite was discovered in the Canyon Diablo meteorite in 1966 (Fronzel and Marvin, 1967) and synthesized earlier that same year (Bundy and

Kasper, 1967), Researchers are still debating its stability and independent existence (Shumilova et al., 2011).

Panguite has high defect density and contains Ti^{4+} and Sc^{3+} making it an interesting candidate for high ion conductivity at elevated temperatures (Ma et al., 2012). Panguite was discovered in the Allende meteorite and is “one of the oldest minerals in the Solar System” (Ma et al., 2012), formed at high pressure potentially during a very early shock wave (Ma et al., 2011a).

Tetrataenite has been investigated for permanent magnet applications and holds good potential as a superior rare-earth-free permanent magnet (Lewis et al., 2014). Tetrataenite is an ultra-rare, highly ordered, non-cubic Fe-Ni alloy mineral that typically forms from the distortion of face-centered cubic (fcc) taenite due to extremely slow cooling (Nayak and Meyer, 2015). It is present in significant amounts only in meteorites with cooling rates of a few degrees per million years over the temperature interval of 700-350°C (Wood 1964; Goldstein and Short 1967). However, this Fe-Ni phase can only be produced on a small (<1 g) scale synthetically (Pauleve et al., 1962; Chamberod et al., 1979; Lima et al., 2003). Large-scale production has not yet been successful.

3.7 Conclusions and Future Work

We have presented a catalog of 66 meteorite minerals. The study of meteorite minerals will have implications for the formation conditions of the early Solar System. Those would benefit greatly from dating of all chondrules, inclusions and matrices in which meteorite minerals have been found. Combined with information of conditions necessary for synthesis, where applicable, and structural clues towards the temperature and pressure conditions under which the minerals formed, the age of meteorite minerals may help constrain the timeline of the early Solar System and build upon our understanding of planet formation.

Applying dating techniques (e.g. Hernández-Bernal and Solé, 2010) to all chondrules, matrices and inclusions that contain

meteorite minerals may provide further insight into the formation conditions in the early Solar System.

An extensive first principles analysis of the total-energy required to create these mineralogical structures (Huang et al., 2013) may shed light on their formation.

Finally, some meteorite minerals could have technologically useful properties not matched by terrestrial materials. Therefore they may be of interest in material science by pointing to novel stable forms.

This catalog is intended to each access to the literature on meteorite mineral so that their potential can be more rapidly realized.

We welcome additions and corrections to our database and will credit all contributions in our online database. We thank Marco Tantardini for raising these questions.

Table 3.5 Meteorite mineral occurrence and distribution

Mineral	Type Meteorite (Chem. Class.)	Mineral Discovery	Crystal Habit	Other Occurrences
Adrianite	Allende (CV3)	Ma and Krot, 2014		
Akimotoite	Tehnam (L6)			Sixiangkou (L6), Zagami (martian), Umbarger (L6)
Allabogdanite	Onello (iron, ungrouped)	Britvin et al., 2002	Forms thin lamellar crystals up to 0.4×0.1×0.01 mm	
Allendeite	Allende (CV3)	Ma et al., 2014		
Andreyivanovite	Kaidun (CR2)	Zolensky et al., 2008	Individual grains and as linear arrays of grains with maximum diameter 8 μm	
Barringerite				
Brearleyite	NWA 1934 (CV3)	Ma et al., 2011	Small (80-300 nm) crystals forming fine-grained aggregates (1×1 μm to 20×60 μm)	
Brezinaite	Tucson (iron, ungrouped, ataxitic)	Bunch and Fuchs, 1968	Anhedral grains 5-80 μm across, most commonly contiguous to silicate inclusions	New Baltimore (Iron-ungr), Sikhote Alin (IIAB)
Brianite	Dayton (IAB)	Fuchs et al., 1967	In small inclusions within a metal matrix as lamellar 4mm×2mm grains	
Browneite	Zakłodzie (ungr. enst achon.)	Ma et al., 2012	Single 16μm grain surrounded by plagioclase	
Buchwaldite	Cape York (IIIAB iron)	Olsen et al., 1977	Minute, polycrystalline, needle-like inclusions in Troilite of ~10-40 μm	
Burnettite	Allende (CV3)	Ma, 2013	Micron-sized euhedral crystals within aluminous melilite	
Buseckite	Zakłodzie (ungr. enst achon.)	Ma et al., 2012	Irregular to sub-hedral, single-crystal grains (4–20 μm in size)	
Carlsbergite	Sikhote-Alin (IIAB)	Axon, 1981	Oriented microscopic platelets, irregular to feathery grains in troilite	Descubridora (IIIAB), New Baltimore (Iron-ungr), Cape York (IIIB)
Chukanovite	Dronino (ataxite)	Pekov et al., 2007	Acicular to fibrous individual grains up to 0.5 mm long and up to 2-3 μm thick	
Cohenite	Magura (IAB iron)			
Davisite	Allende (CV3)	Ma and Rossman, 2009	Fine-grained aggregate of irregular to sub-hedral crystals with width of 2-12 μm	
Daubréelite	Coahuila (IIAB)	Smith, 1876	Massive, platy aggregates, exsolution lamellae in troilite	Broadly dispersed across meteorite groups.
Dmitryivanovite	NWA470 (CH3)	Mikouchi et al., 2009	~10μm sub-hedral grains	
Droninoite	Dronino (iron, ungrouped)	Chukanov et al., 2010	Fine-grained segregations up to 0.15 x 1 x 1 mm	
Farringtonite	Springwater (PMG)	Du Fresne and Roy, 1961	Sub-hedral to euhedral grains, to 2 mm, and as rims on olivine	Krasnojarsk (PMG-an), Zaisho (PMG-an), Imilac (PMG), and Port Oxford (PMG)
Florenskyite	Kaidun (CR2)	Ivanov et al., 2000	Anhedral and sub-hedral grains of ~14μm within a single mass of Fe-rich serpentine	
Grossite	Leoville (CV3)	Michel-Lévy et al., 1982	Highly birefringent blebs, mostly 5-10μm wide	
Grossmanite	Allende (CV3)	Ma and Rossman, 2009		
Hapkeite	Dhofar 280 (lunar)	Anand et al., 2003	Grains of ~35μm or smaller. Exhibits complex inter-growths of two or more phases	

Mineral	Type Meteorite (Chem. Class.)	Mineral Discovery	Crystal Habit	Other Occurrences
Haxonite	Toluca (IAB-sLL), Canyon Diablo (IA)	Scott, 1971		Common in iron meteorites and carbonaceous chondrites
Heideite	Bustee (aubrite)	Keil and Brett, 1974	Minute anhedral grains, up to 100µm	Kaidun (CR2)
Hexamolybdenum	Allende (CV3)	Ma et al., 2014	Euhedral metallic grains of 0.2–1.2 µm in diameter occur as inclusions in allendite and a Zr-Y-rich perovskite	
Hibonite-(Fe)	Allende (CV3)	Ma, 2010	Scattered single crystals of 1–4 µm in size in the central area of a highly altered CAI	
Hutcheonite	Allende (CV3)	Ma and Krot, 2014	Small, irregular single crystals 500 nm to 4 µm in size	
Kamacite	Tuscon (iron, ung)	Bunch and Fuchs, 1969	Massive - uniformly indistinguishable crystals forming large masses	Ubiquitous in iron meteorites
Kangite	Allende (CV3)	Ma et al., 2013	Micrometer-sized, irregular to sub-hedral grains of 1 - 4 µm	
Keilite	Abee (EH4)	Shimizu et al., 2002	Xenomorphic grains up to 0.5 mm in diameter	Present in at least 20 Enstatite chondrites
Krinovite	Canyon Diablo (IA)	Olsen and Fuchs, 1968	Disseminated 200 µm sub-hedral grains within graphite nodules	Wichita county (IAB), Younegin (IAB)
Krotite	NWA 1934 (CV3)	Ma et al., 2011	Aggregates ranging from 10 – 350 µm	Zaklodzie (enst achon-ung)
Lonsdaleite	Canyon Diablo (IA)			Kenna (Ureilite), Allan Hills 77283 (IAB-MG)
Majindeite	Allende (CV3)	Ma, 2013	Sub-micron sub-hedral grains and euhedral nanolaths	
Majorite	Coorara (L6)	Smith and Mason, 1970		Sixiangkou (L6)
Merrihueite	Mezo-Madaras (L3.7)	Dodd et al., 1965	Inclusions in enstatite as aggregates of to 150 µm made up of smaller individual grains	Mezo-Madaras (L3.7)
Merrillite	Allegan (H5)	Shannon and Larsen, 1925	Anhedral grains and is a H-free analog of terrestrial whitlockite.	Sombrerete (IAB-sHL), Shergotty (Martian)
Moissanite	Canyon Diablo (IA)			
Moniptite	Allende (CV3)	Ma et al., 2014	One 1 × 2 mm crystal in a Type B1 Ca-Al-rich inclusion	
Murchisite	Murchison (CM2)	Ma et al., 2011	Two ~1 µm sub-hedral grains found in an olivine grain	
Nierite	Adrar 003 (LL3.2)	Lee et al., 1995	Very small (~2× 0.4 µm) lath-shaped grains	Inman (L3.4), Tieschitz (H3.6), Indarch (EH4)
Niningerite	Abee (EH4)	Keil and Snetsinger, 1967	Intimately intergrown with metallic nickel-iron and troilite	Present in at least 8 other EH meteorites
Nuwaite	Allende (CV3)	Ma, 2013	Irregular grains, 1-6 µm in size in alteration veins or filling some cracks in primary melilite in the CAI	
Oldhamite	Bustee (aubrite)	Maskelyne, 1870	Small, nearly round spherules (4mm) imbedded in enstatite or augite, or in a mixture of both	All enstatite chondrites
Osbornite	Bustee (aubrite)	Bannister, 1941	Microscopic regular octahedra found in oldhamite	
Panethite	Dayton (iron, very fine octahedrite)	Fuchs, 1967	Small inclusions within a metal matrix	
Panguite	Allende (CV3)	Ma et al., 2012	Small irregular to sub-hedral crystals (~0.5 - 2 µm), consistently in contact with davisite	Murchison (CM2), SaU 290 (CH3)
Paqueite	Allende (CV3)	Ma et al., 2013	Micron-sized euhedral crystals within aluminous melilite	

Mineral	Type Meteorite (Chem. Class.)	Mineral Discovery	Crystal Habit	Other Occurrences
Ringwoodite	Sixiangkou (L6)	Chen et al., 2004	Lamellae that form platelets from several unit cells to 100 nm in thickness	
Roaldite	Youndegin (IAB-MG)	Buchwald and Nielson, 1981	Irregularly dispersed planar foils 1-2 μm thick and many millimeters long	Youndegin (IAB), Jerslev (IIAB), Maribo (CM2), Canyon Diablo (IA)
Rudashevskyite	Indarch (EH4)	Britvin et al., 2008	Xenomorphic polycrystalline grains, 5–120 μm in size	
Schreibersite	Ollague (pallasite)			Lunar highland rocks, Magura (IAB), Sikhote Alin (IIAB)
Sinoite	Jajh deh Kot Lalu (EH6)	Keil and Anderson, 1965	Grains of up to 200 μm in length.	Hvittis (EL6), Ufana (EL6), Pillistfer (EL6), Neuschwanstein (EL6)
Stanfieldite	Estherville (Mes)	Fuchs, 1967	Sub-hedral to irregular grains, to 1 mm, in veinlets and rimming olivine.	Albin (PMG), Finmarken (PMG), Imilac (PMG), Newport (PMG), Mount Vernon (PMG), Santa Rosalia (PMG), and Zaisho (PMG-an)
Steinhardtite	Khatyrka (CV3)	Bindi et al., 2014	Rare anhedral crystals up to ~10 μm across in meteoritic fragments that contain evidence of a heterogeneous distribution of pressures and temperatures during impact shock	
Taenite	Canyon Diablo (IA)			Campo del Cielo (IAB), Henbury (IIIAB)
Tetrataenite Tistarite	Allende (CV3)	Ma and Rossman, 2009	One isolated grain within a cluster of refractory grains discovered in situ in a ferromagnesian chondrule	
Troilite	Albareto (L/LL4)			
Ureyite	Coahuila (IIAB)	Frondel and Klein, 1965	A smooth lenticel of about 0.5 mm in size made up of a polycrystalline aggregate of prismatic cleavage fragments up to 200 μm in size.	Toluca (IAB), Hex River Mtns (IIAB)
Wadsleyite	Peace River (L6)	Price et al., 1983)	A fine-grained material in fragments, rarely exceeding 5 μm in diameter	
Wassonite	Yamato 691 (EH3)	Nakamura-Messenger, et al., 2012	Grains of < 0.5 μm in diameter within the mesostasis of the BO chondrule	
Yagiite	Colomera (IIE)	Bunch and Fuchs, 1969	Interstitial in a 0.8 mm silicate inclusion surrounded by nickel-iron, found in 6 silicate inclusions, making up ~1% vol.	

Table 3.6 Meteorite mineral physical properties

Mineral	Unit Cell	Crystal Structure	Hardness	Density (g/cm ³)	Cleavage/Fracture
Allabogdanite	a = 5.748(2) Å, b = 3.548(1) Å, c = 6.661(2) Å; Z = 4	Orthorhombic - dipyramidal, 2/m 2/m 2/m, Pnma	5 - 6	7.10	None
Allendeite	a = 9.396 Å, c = 8.720 Å, V = 666.7 Å ³ ; Z = 3	Trigonal, R $\bar{3}$		4.84 (calc)	
Andreyivanovite	a = 5.833(1) Å, b = 3.569(1) Å, c = 6.658(1) Å; Z = 4	Orthorhombic - dipyramidal, 2/m 2/m 2/m, Pnma			
Barringerite	a = 5.87 ± 0.07 Å, c = 3.44 ± 0.04 Å	Hexagonal, P $\bar{6}$ 2m			
Brearleyite	a = 11.98(8) Å, V = 1719.1 Å ³ ; Z = 2	Isometric, I $\bar{4}$ 3d		2.797 (calc)	
Brezinaite	a = 5.96 Å, b = 3.42 Å, c = 11.27 Å; β = 91°32', V = 229.97 Å ³	Monoclinic, 2/m, I2/m	3.5 - 4.5	4.12 (calc)	
Brianite	a = 13.36 Å, b = 5.23 Å, c = 9.13 Å; β = 91.2°	Monoclinic prismatic, 2/m, P 21/a	4 - 5	3.17 (calc), 3.0-3.3 (meas)	None
Browneite	a = 5.601 Å, V = 175.71 Å ³ ; Z = 4	Isometric, F $\bar{4}$ 3m		3.291 (calc)	
Buchwaldite	a = 5.167 Å, b = 9.259 Å, c = 6.737 Å, Z = 4	Orthorhombic, mm2, Pmn2 ₁	< 3	3.21 (calc)	One platy cleavage/ parting
Buseckite	a = 3.8357 Å, c = 6.3002 Å, V = 80.27 Å ³ ; Z = 2	Hexagonal, P6 ₃ mc		3.697 (calc)	
Carlsbergite	a = 4.16 Å; Z = 4	Isometric, 4/m $\bar{3}$ 2/m, Fm3m	7	5.9	
Chukanovite	a = 12.396(1) Å, b = 9.407(1) Å, c = 3.2152(3) Å, β = 97.78°; Z = 1	Monoclinic, 2/m P2 ₁ /a	3.5 - 4	3.60 (calc)	Uneven fracture, perfect cleavage, probably on {0,-2,1}
Davisite	a = 9.884 Å, b = 8.988 Å, c = 5.446 Å, β = 105.86°, V = 465.39 Å ³ ; Z = 12	Monoclinic, 2/m, C 2/c		3.38 (calc)	No twinning
Daubréelite	a = 9.966 Å; Z = 8	Isometric, 4/m $\bar{3}$ 2/m, Fm3m	4.5 - 5		Distinct cleavage, uneven fracture
Dmitryivanovite	a = 7.95 Å, b = 8.62 Å, c = 10.25 Å; β = 93.1°; Z = 12	Monoclinic prismatic, 2/m, P2 ₁ /c			
Droninoite	a = 6.206(2) Å, c = 46.184(18) Å, V = 1540.4(8) Å ³ ; Z = 6	Rhombohedral, R $\bar{3}$ m	1 - 1.5	2.857 (calc)	By analogy hydrotalcite group, good on {001}

Mineral	Unit Cell	Crystal Structure	Hardness	Density (g/cm ³)	Cleavage/Fracture
Farringtonite	a = 8.79(1) Å, b = 8.22(2) Å, c = 5.07(1) Å, β = 120.5(5)°; Z = 2	Monoclinic, 2/m, P2 ₁ /a			{100} and {010}, fair to good
Florenskyite	a = 6.007(1) Å, b = 3.602(1) Å, c = 6.897(1) Å; Z = 4	Orthorhombic dipyramidal, 2/m 2/m 2/m, Pnma			
Grossmanite	a = 9.80 Å, b = 8.85 Å, c = 5.36 Å, β = 105.62°, V = 447.70 Å ³ ; Z = 4	Monoclinic, C 2/c		3.41 (calc)	
Hapkeite	a = 2.831 Å, V = 22.69 Å ³ ; Z = 2	Isometric, Pm3m			
Haxonite	a = 10.55 Å; Z = 4 (by analogy)	Isometric	5.5 - 6	7.70 (calc)	
Heideite	a = 5.97 Å, b = 3.42 Å, c = 11.4 Å ³ , β = 90.2°; Z = 2	Monoclinic, 2/m, I2/m	3.5 - 4.5	3.993 (calc)	Indistinct
Hexamolybdenum	a = 2.7506 Å, c = 4.4318 Å, V = 29.04 Å ³ ; Z = 2	Hexagonal, P6 ₃ /mmc		11.99 (calc)	
Hibonite-(Fe)	a = 5.613 Å, c = 22.285 Å, V = 608.0 Å ³ ; Z = 2	Hexagonal, P6 ₃ /mmc		3.61 (calc)	
Hutcheonite	a = 11.843 Å, V = 1661.06 Å ³ ; Z = 8	Isometric, Ia $\bar{3}$ d		3.86.99 (calc)	
Kamacite	a = 8.60 Å; Z = 54	Isometric, 4/m $\bar{3}$ 2/m, Fm3m	4	7.9	Indistinct cleavage, Hackly - Jagged fracture, torn surfaces, (e.g. fractured metals).
Kangite	a = 9.842(1) Å, V = 953.3 Å ³ ; Z = 16	Isotropic, cation- deficient Ia $\bar{3}$ bixbyite subgroup		3.879 (calc)	
Keilite	a = 5.172 Å, V = 138.32 Å ³ ; Z = 4	Isometric, 4/m $\bar{3}$ 2/m, Fm3m	4	3.958	Good, parallel to {001}, {010}, and {100}
Krinovite	a = 10.238(4) Å, b = 10.642(4) Å, c = 8.780(3) Å, α = 105.15(3)°, β = 96.50(4)°, γ = 125.15(3)°; Z = 2	Triclinic, pseudo- monoclinic, P $\bar{1}$	5.5-7.0	3.38	None
Krotite	a = 8.6996(3) Å, b = 8.0994(3) Å, c = 15.217(1) Å, β = 90.188(6)°; Z = 12	Monoclinic, 2/m, P2 ₁ /n	~6.5	2.944 (calc)	Good cleavage on {100} and {010}, Conchoidal fracture
Majindeite	a = 5.778 Å, c = 9.904 Å, V = 286.35 Å ³ ; Z = 2	Hexagonal, P6 ₃ mc		5.54 (calc)	

Mineral	Unit Cell	Crystal Structure	Hardness	Density (g/cm ³)	Cleavage/Fracture
Merrihueite	a = 10.16±0.06 Å, c = 14.32±0.06 Å; Z=2	Hexagonal, 6/m 2/m 2/ m, P6/mcc (by analogy)		2.87 (calc)	
Merrillite	a = 10.362 Å, c = 37.106 Å; Z = 6	Trigonal ditrigonal pyramidal, 3m, R3c		3.1	Poor - indistinct cleavage
Moniptite	a = 5.861 Å, c = 3.704 Å, V = 110.19 Å ³ ; Z = 3	Hexagonal, P6̄2m		8.27 (calc)	
Murchisite	a = 5.982 Å, c = 11.509 Å, V = 356.67 Å ³ ; Z = 2	Hexagonal, P3̄1c		4.22 (calc)	
Nierite	a = 7.758 Å, c = 5.623 Å, V = 293.1 Å ³ ; Z = 4	Trigonal, P31c, 3m	9	3.11 (calc)	
Niningerite	a = 5.17 Å	Isometric hextetrahedral, 4/m 3̄ 2/m, Pm3m	3.5 - 4		
Nuwaite	a = 3.65 Å, c = 18.14 Å, V = 241.7 Å ³ ; Z = 2				
Oldhamite	a = 5.69 Å; Z = 4	Isometric hextetrahedral, 4/m 3̄ 2/m, Pm3m	4	2.58	Good cleavage on {001}
Osbornite	a = 4.235 Å; Z = 4	Isometric hextetrahedral, 4/m 3̄ 2/m, Pm3m			
Panethite	a = 10.18 Å, b = 14.90 Å, c = 25.87 Å, β = 91.1°	Monoclinic - prismatic, 2/m, P2 ₁ /n		2.99 (calc), 2.9-3.0 (meas)	Indistinct cleavage
Panguite	a = 9.781(1) Å, b = 9.778(2) Å, c = 9.815(1) Å, V = 938.7 Å ³ ; Z = 16	Orthorhombic - dipyramidal, 2/m 2/m 2/m, Pbca, Ia3 bixbyite subgroup		3.746 (calc)	
Roaldite	a = 3.79 Å; Z = 1	Isometric hextetrahedral, 4/m 3̄ 2/m, Pm3m	5.5 - 6.5	7.21	
Rudashevskyite	a = 5.426(2) Å, V = 159.8(2) Å ³ ; Z = 4	Isometric, F4̄3m		3.79 (calc)	
Sinoite	a = 8.84 Å, b = 5.47 Å, c = 4.83 Å; Z = 4	Orthorhombic – pyramidal, mm2, Cmc2 ₁		2.83	None
Stanfieldite	a = 17.16(3) Å, b = 10.00(2) Å, c = 22.88(4) Å, β = 100°15(10)'; Z = 8	Monoclinic, P2/c or Pc, 2/m or m	4.5 - 5	3.15	
Steinhardtite	a = 3.0214(8) Å, V = 27.58(2) Å ³ ; Z = 2	Isometric, Im3̄m		5.52 (calc)	
Tistarite	a = 5.158 Å, c = 13.611 Å, V = 313.61 Å ³ ; Z = 6	Rhombohedral, R3̄c		4.53 (calc)	

Mineral	Unit Cell	Crystal Structure	Hardness	Density (g/cm ³)	Cleavage/Fracture
Ureyite	a = 9.560 ± 0.16 Å, b = 8.746 ± 0.008 Å, c = 5.270 ± 0.006 Å, β = 107.38 ± 0.10° V = 420.6 ± 1.1 Å ³ ; Z = 12	Monoclinic, C 2/c		3.60 (calc)	Well-defined cleavage on (110) and pronounced parting on (001)
Wadsleyite	a = 5.70(2) Å, b = 11.51(7) Å, c = 8.24(4) Å, V = 541(3) Å ³ ; Z = 8	Orthorhombic		3.84 (calc)	
Wassonite	a = 3.42 ± 0.07 Å, c = 26.50 ± 0.53 Å, V = 268.4 ± 0.53 Å ³ ; Z = 9	Rhombohedral, R $\bar{3}$ m		4.452 (calc)	
Yagiite	a = 10.09(1) Å, c = 14.29(3) Å; Z = 2	Hexagonal, P6/mcc, 6/m 2/m 2/m		2.70 (calc)	

Table 7. Meteorite mineral optical properties

Mineral	Color	Lustre	Diaphaneity	Optics
Allabogdanite	Light straw-yellow	Bright Metallic		
Allendeite				
Andreyivanovite	Creamy white in reflected light	Metallic		
Brearleyite	Light olive green		Transparent	Isotropic
Brezinaite	Brownish gray	Dull Metallic	Opaque	
Brianite	Colorless	Vitreous	Transparent	Biaxial (-)
Browneite	Yellow-Brown		Translucent	
Buchwaldite	Colorless in transmitted light		Semitransparent	Biaxial (-)
Buseckite	black in diffuse light, grayish brown in transmitted light		Near-Opaque	
Carlsbergite	Light gray in reflected light with rose tint	Metallic	Opaque	
Chukanovite	Pale-green or colorless if unaltered, surface of aggregates is brownish-green	Vitreous	Transparent	Biaxial (-)
Davisite	Light gray		Transparent	
Daubréelite	Black	Metallic		
Dmitryivanovite	Colorless in PPL			
Droninoite	Dark gray-green	Dull		
Farringtonite	Colorless, white, yellow, dark amber		Transparent to opaque	Biaxial (+)
Florenskyite	Creamy white in reflected light	Metallic		
Grossmanite	Light gray		Transparent	
Hapkeite	Silvery, with a slight tarnish	Metallic	Opaque	
Haxonite	Brilliant white		Opaque	Isotropic
Heideite	Creamy white in reflected light		Opaque	
Hexamolybdenum		Metallic		
Hibonite-(Fe)				
Hutcheonite				
Kamacite	Iron black, steel gray	Metallic		
Kangite			Opaque	
Keilite	Bluish-gray in reflected light	Metallic	Opaque	Isotropic
Krinovite	Deep emerald green			Biaxial (+)
Krotite	Colorless	Vitreous	Transparent	Biaxial (-)
Majindeite				
Merrhueite	Colorless to greenish blue			Uniaxial or biaxial
Merrillite	Colorless to white	Vitreous		Uniaxial (-)
Moniptite			Opaque	
Murchisite	Opaque to transmitted light, gray in reflected light			
Nierite		Adamantine		
Niningerite	Gray	Metallic	Opaque	Isotropic
Nuwaite				

Mineral	Color	Lustre	Diaphaneity	Optics
Oldhamite	Pale chestnut-brown	Sub-metallic	Transparent	Isotropic
Osbornite	Golden yellow	Metallic	Opaque	
Panethite	Amber		Transparent	Biaxial (-)
Panguite			Opaque	
Roaldite	White	Metallic	Opaque	Isotropic
Rudashevskyite	Black	Resinous to submetallic		
Sinoite	Colorless to light gray	Vitreous	Transparent to translucent	Biaxial (-)
Stanfieldite	Red-amber, weathers to pale blue, colorless in transmitted light		Transparent	
Taenite	Dark gray			
Tetrataenite	Cream			
Tistarite	Gray		Opaque	
Ureyite	Emerald green			
Wadsleyite	Pale fawn		Transparent	
Wassonite	Dark bronze to brown (synth)			
Yagiite	Colorless			Uniaxial (+)

4. Iron Meteorite Trace Element Abundance Database

Iron meteorites play an important role in developing theories of planetesimal core cooling. Cooling processes are studied by measuring the distribution and partitioning of trace elements within iron meteorites. With 135 independent groups of meteorites (Meibom and Clark, 1999) and trace element abundances spanning up to 4 orders of magnitude within some groups, large quantities of data are necessary for developing models. Motivated by the need for data, we performed an extensive literature review and compiled a database of iron meteorite trace element data. We present a database of nickel and 16 trace elements from 708 iron meteorites. The trace element abundances reported are Cr, Co, Cu, Ga, Ge, As, Sb, W, Re, Ir, Pt, Pd, Rh, Ru, Os and Au. The database is stored in excel format and will be available at the CfA web site (www.cfa.harvard.edu). We encourage contributions to this database and hope that it will highlight gaps within the current literature.

4.1 Introduction

The study of meteorites provides us with a window to the composition and formation of the asteroids from which they are derived. Magmatic iron meteorites, in particular, provide information on the cooling of planetesimal cores.

Most (86%) iron meteorites can be assigned to one of 12 genetic groups on the

basis of systematic variations in their chemical, mineralogical, and structural properties; the remaining 14% are termed anomalous. The groups are best resolved on Ga-Ni or Ge-Ni plots, but they may also be defined using other elements, the distribution and morphology of characteristic minerals, and very often kamacite bandwidths. The power of this classification to reveal correlations of

numerous and diverse properties within these, groups and systematic variations between groups emphasize the validity of the classification scheme.

To better visualize the distribution of trace element abundance across different classes of iron meteorites we have compiled a database providing abundance data for 16 trace elements. This database is ~45% complete with a large number of values missing because a number of papers from which we scraped data were performing selective analyses of certain elements.

While the database is not complete, it has already proven to be a useful tool in mapping trace element abundances against each other in 2- and 3-dimensions (Chapter 5). We encourage contributions to this database and hope that it will highlight gaps within the current literature that may be worthwhile filling.

4.2 Database Aggregation and Contents

The literature on iron meteorite trace element abundances is somewhat scattered. I have created a database of trace abundance measurements for Ga, Ge, Ir, Pt, Pd, Ru, Os, Rh, Re, Au, Cu, Cr, As, W and Sb all of which are measured in $\mu\text{g/g}$ in addition to Ni and Co, which are measured in mg/g . To compile this database of meteorite trace element abundances I scraped data from 23 papers from 1967-2005. This database includes 708 iron meteorites of the ~1150 known.

The earliest papers reported data for only Ni, Ga and Ge. Papers that contain data pertaining to PGE-bearing iron meteorites became more numerous after 1980. Only measurements of iridium (Ir) concentration were recorded initially and as a result, Ir abundance values are available for all meteorites listed. Gold (Au) concentration values are reported for ~57.7% of the meteorites and platinum (Pt) concentration values are reported for ~39.5% of meteorites in our database. Least frequently reported are concentrations of palladium (Pd), (Ru) and (Rh) which are only reported for the same 119 meteorites. In total the database is 46% complete. All meteorites have data reported for Ni and all but one have data for Ir.

Figure 4.1 - Left: Plot of Ir (ppm) vs Ni (%) for irons (Scott et al., 1970). The dashed line around group IAB indicates a more diffuse boundary. Right: Plot of Ir ($\mu\text{g/g}$) vs Ni (mg/g) for irons (this work). All ungrouped irons have been excluded from this plot for neatness.

4.3 Discussion

This database provides improved visualization of the abundance ranges of trace elements within iron meteorites. Figure 4.1 shows updates to the Scott et al., (1970) plot of Ir vs. Ni. The number of group IAB irons (in dark blue on our plot) that have been analyzed for Ni and Ir content since 1970 has increased significantly and is more dispersed in Ir-Ni space than previously thought.

This database can be used for 3-dimensional visualizations. Figure 4.2 shows 3D plots of Ni vs. Ga vs. Ge. Goldberg et al., (1951)

determined that there is quantized grouping of Ga in Ga-Ni space. Six years later, Lovering et al., (1957) identified similar grouping in Ge-Ni space and noted that Ga and Ge are positive correlated within all iron meteorite groups. While most groups have maintained a tight clustering, group IAB is again quite dispersed. Statistical clustering analyses may be a good way to explore these groupings.

With a more complete database and the continual discovery of meteorites, we hope this database will serve as a tool to explore grouping of iron meteorites by trace elements.

Figure 4.2 - 3D plots of Ni (mg/g) vs. Ga ($\mu\text{g/g}$) vs. Ge ($\mu\text{g/g}$) at different Ga and Ge are the basis for the standard iron meteorite chemical classification scheme. Different iron meteorite groups are colored according to the key on the right.

4.4 Conclusions and Future Work

Analyses of trace elements have highlighted the richness of asteroids in precious metals, in particular the platinum group elements (PGEs). As highly siderophile, or “iron-loving”, elements (HSEs), PGEs play an important role in developing theories of planet formation and there may be much to gain from mapping their distribution within asteroids. This high abundance

of PGEs, amongst other things, also makes asteroids an important target for establishing a commercial market in space (see Chapter 5).

We have compiled a database of 708 iron meteorite and their trace element abundances. This database has numerous applications, including but not limited to: exploring element-element correlations and statistical clustering of trace elements.

5. Prospecting Asteroids for Platinum Group Metals

We find that careful selection of Fe meteorites based on Ni abundance can efficiently select meteorites with high PGE concentrations. In particular, there are three distinct groups of meteorites (IIAB, IID, IVB), believed to originate in separate parent bodies, that have a Pt concentration exceeding 20 $\mu\text{g/g}$ in 60%, 50% and 100% of meteorites, respectively. Of these 3 groups, IIAB and IVB have well-defined Ni concentrations that allow them to be picked out readily. Of the 120 meteorites with all PGE values recorded, we find an average total PGE value of 35.43 $\mu\text{g/g}$, with the highest total PGM count at 180.9 $\mu\text{g/g}$. I also present three methods for determining, statistically, the Pt content of a particular asteroid; laser ablation, x-ray fluorescence and γ -ray spectroscopy.

5.1 Introduction

Asteroid mining has been featured in science fiction novels and films since Garrett P. Serviss' novel *Edisons Conquest of Mars* (1898). Once confined to the imagination of creative writers, asteroid mining may soon become a reality. *Planetary Resources*¹⁵ (PR), formed in 2010, was the first company created with the mission to mine asteroids. A second asteroid mining company, *Deep Space Industries*¹⁶ (DSI), was formed in 2013. While both of these companies are yet to mine any asteroids, they

have brought asteroid mining into popular discourse¹⁷.

Both companies are most interested in extracting water from C-type (carbonaceous) asteroids, as water is relatively easy to extract. However, there is also discussion of mining asteroids for precious metals, in particular platinum group elements (PGEs), from metallic asteroids.

Here we seek to quantify the distribution of platinum (Pt) concentrations across iron meteorite groups with a view to determining their value as metallic asteroid ore bodies. Pt is not the

¹⁵ <http://planetaryresources.com/>

¹⁶ <http://deepspaceindustries.com/>

¹⁷ http://www.nytimes.com/2012/04/24/science/space/in-pursuit-of-riches-and-travelers-supplies-in-the-asteroid-belt.html?_r=0

only valuable metal that might be extracted from metallic asteroids, but it was chosen for this analysis because we have sufficient data for meaningful analysis and because PR and DSI both feature it on their websites as a potential future mission. The method we present for exploring the content of Pt can easily be applied to other precious metals.

We study meteoritic concentrations of Pt as a function of Ni abundance. Ni was chosen because it is present in iron meteorites at levels of $\sim 10\text{-}100$ mg/g and is therefore more easily detectable than Pt, which is present at levels of ~ 10 $\mu\text{g/g}$. In Section 5.4 we analyze the usefulness of Ni as a proxy for Pt content in proximity surveys. This work assumes that iron

Figure 5.1 - Plots of Ni (mg/g) vs. Pt ($\mu\text{g/g}$). (a) Meteorite groups are color coded and shown in the key to the right. We define Pt-rich bands by the blue shaded regions labelled IIAB-band, IID-band and IVB-band. Meteorites with Pt ($\mu\text{g/g}$) > 20 that do not fall into the three Pt-rich bands are circled in green. (b) Ni vs. Pt with a log scale on the y-axis. Groups IIAB, IID and IVB are highlighted. This plot was made with a total of 296 iron meteorites.

meteorites are an unbiased sample of metallic asteroid compositions.

5.2 PGEs in Iron Meteorites

For the analysis of precious metal profitability, I have utilized a database of trace abundance measurements for Ir, Pt, Pd, Ru, Os and Rh (Chapter 4). These trace elements are present at $\mu\text{g/g}$ levels. Ni is also present in iron meteorites at $\sim 1000\times$ higher levels, mg/g .

Data pertaining to PGE-bearing iron meteorites became numerous during the 1980s. Initially, only measurements of iridium (Ir) concentration were recorded. As a result, Ir abundance values are available for all meteorites listed. Platinum (Pt) concentration values are reported for $\sim 40\%$ of meteorites in our database. Least frequently reported are concentrations of palladium (Pd), (Ru) and (Rh) which are only reported for the same 119 meteorites. In total the database is 45% complete for PGE data. All meteorites have data reported for Ni and all but one have data for Ir.

5.3 Pt Abundance by Meteorite Group

Each iron meteorite group is believed to originate in a unique meteorite parent body.

Therefore, to assess the value for a prospecting mission, the best we can do is determine the relative abundance of platinum group metals within a particular group of iron meteorites and compare that to the average PGM abundance of all iron meteorites. This is analogous to selecting a statistically high-PGM asteroid versus selecting an M-type asteroid at random.

As can be seen in Figure 5.1, certain groups of iron meteorites have significantly higher platinum abundances than others. In three iron meteorite groups (IIAB, IID and IVB) Pt is present at levels of $20 \mu\text{g/g}$ for 50% or more of the meteorites within that group. We have identified these as the most promising candidates.

Table 5.1 - Concentrations of PGEs in South African and Russian in situ Ores*

Element	Concentration, or grade, of 'in situ' ore, $\mu\text{g/g}$
Pd	2-7
Pt	2-4
Rh	0.2-0.5
Ru	0.3-0.7
Ir	0.1-0.2
Os	0.04-0.1
Total	7-10

*'As-mined' concentrations of ore are as much as 40% lower than in situ concentrations of ore, because the ore is diluted with rock during underground mining. *Anglo American Platinum, 2009; Impala Platinum, 2008.

Earth-based mines can have average Pt abundances as low as $0.3 \mu\text{g/g}$ Pt while

considered profitable. Most mines have Pt abundance ranging from 2 - 4 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and total PGE abundance from 7-10 $\mu\text{g/g}$ (Table 5.1). That is, on average, meteorites have higher Pt than the total PGE of Earth-based mines.

The Pt abundances for all available iron meteorites have been binned by $\text{Pt}(\mu\text{g/g})=5$ and plotted in a histogram (Figure 5.2). We make the following observations:

- ◆ Range of Pt is a factor of 10 with outliers to 20X.
- ◆ Pt abundance in meteorites can be \gg than in Earth mines

However, platinum and all other PGMs typically have abundances on the order of 1-50 ppm. Furthermore, iron meteorite groups are distinguished by Ga and Ge abundance, not readily measurable outside the lab. Measuring these abundances directly would require visiting each candidate asteroid and performing trace element analysis which would be costly and time consuming. In order to pick out high-PGE asteroids, we need a proxy that can be measured with less precision.

5.3.1 Search for proxies of high Pt abundance

Figure 5.1 shows that these Pt-rich meteorite types are concentrated in several bands

Figure 5.2 - Platinum distribution, by fraction, across iron meteorites. Both group IID and group IVB (colored yellow and green, respectively) are most heavily weighted to the higher end of the scale while IIAB peaks at 5 and 30 $\mu\text{g/g}$. On average, all iron meteorites show decreased frequency as Pt abundance increases.

of quite tightly delineated Ni-abundance ranges. Ni is present in iron meteorites with typical abundances of 40-200 mg/g. By eye it appears that Ni is a reasonable proxy for groups IIAB, IID and IVB. In Table 5.2 I provide the standard deviation from the mean, and the min and max abundance of both Pt and Ni in all iron meteorites and by type. In Section 5.4 I quantitatively determine the value of a Ni proxy for Pt abundance.

5.4 Measurement Statistics

While it is believed that all meteorites within a group came from a single parent body, we do not know if they necessarily correspond to a single asteroid. If an original parent body smashed up into smaller asteroids, it is possible

Figure 5.3 - Plots of Ni (mg/g) vs. Pt ($\mu\text{g/g}$). (a) Each of the meteorite groups are color coded and shown in the key to the right. (b) Pt Only groups IIAB, IID and IVB are colored to highlight them amongst all other groups. Circled in green are the meteorites with Pt ($\mu\text{g/g}$) > 20 that are not included in the three Pt-rich bands.

Table 5.2 - The range of Pt and Ni values amongst iron meteorites.

Group	No. of Samples	Pt ($\mu\text{g/g}$)			Ni (mg/g)			
		Mean	Min	Max	Mean	Min	Max	σ
All Irons	296	12.29	0.055	86.4	88.90	41.3	336.2	32.94
IIAB	79	19.91	0.55	37.2	56.89	52.1	64.7	4.26
IID	18	19.40	12.5	23	100.98	96	113	3.81
IVB	9	43.79	29.5	86.4	169.85	158	184	8.31

Table 5.3 - Fraction of meteorites with $\text{Pt} > 20 \mu\text{g/g}$ and in groups IIAB, IID and IVB within Ni-band for perfect measurement and different SNR values.

Band	Ni (mg/g)	Perfect		SNR=20		SNR=10		SNR=5	
		% Pt > 20 $\mu\text{g/g}$	% band group	% Pt > 20 $\mu\text{g/g}$	% band group	% Pt > 20 $\mu\text{g/g}$	% band group	% Pt > 20 $\mu\text{g/g}$	% band group
All	All	23.0%	-	23.0%	-	23.0%	-	23.0%	-
IIAB	52 - 60	71.9%	100.0%	71.9%	100.0%	58.3%	83.3%	38.2%	55.9%
IID	95 - 105	27.3%	48.5%	27.3%	48.5%	16.0%	16.0%	9.5%	9.5%
IVB	155 - 180	83.3%	75.0%	83.3%	75.0%	42.9%	55.6%	42.9%	42.9%

that the trace element composition of each asteroid differs, reflecting the range of Pt values we see within a group of meteorites. Therefore, to assess the probability of an asteroid being Pt-rich, we need to know what fraction of iron meteorites are Pt-rich.

However, if all meteorites within a group come from a single asteroid, then we are interested in the probability that a meteorite within an Ni-band belongs to a Pt-rich group of meteorites.

In this section I evaluate the probability of identifying a Pt-rich asteroid for the two above cases with only Ni abundance measured. Section 5.4.1 discusses the outcomes with perfect measurements and in Section 5.4.2 I simulate spectroscopic measurements with different signal-

to-noise ratios (SNR) by introducing normally distributed error to the meteorite data.

To simulate a variety of observations with different SNRs, I randomized the Ni data with gaussian errors and standard deviation $\sigma = 1/\text{SNR}$. The Ni-values (x-axis, Figure 4.2) were reassigned according to:

$$Ni' = Ni[1 + \text{rand-gauss}(\sigma)]$$

where Ni' is the new Ni value and σ is the standard deviation of the gaussian. We selected $\sigma=0.05,0.1,0.2$, corresponding to $\text{SNR}=20,10,5$, for this analysis. Figure 5.3 shows the new Ni values for each SNR plotted against Pt. The increased likelihood of selecting a high-Pt asteroid if Ni falls within one of the three high-Pt bands is quantified in Figure 5.4 and Table 5.3.

Figure 5.4 - Probability of $Pt=x$ for all iron meteorites, and those in the IIAB-, IID- and IVB-bands. (a) Perfect measurement, (b) SNR = 20, (c) SNR = 10, (d) SNR = 5.

5.4.1 Lab-based High SNR Measurements

Iron meteorite composition is typically measured with instrumental neutron activation analysis (INAA) and is accurate on scales of parts per billion (ppb). Therefore, iron meteorite abundance measurements are a suitable “true value” for the composition of their parent asteroids.

If we select a metallic asteroid mining target of random composition the probability of that asteroid having a high ($>20 \mu\text{g/g}$) Pt content

is ~ 1 in 5 (23%) (Figure 4.2a). The Pt-rich bands (defined in Figure 5.1) contain meteorites that are almost uniformly of one type.

With perfect measurement, selecting a meteorite with Ni in the IIAB-band increases the chance of $Pt(\mu\text{g/g}) > 20$ threefold and the IVB-band nearly fourfold, while IID-band by only 20% (Figure 5.4(a)). The IIAB-band is populated exclusively by IIAB group meteorites, while the IID- and IVB-band are not. Table 5.3 quantifies this data.

Figure 5.5 - Probability of Pt>20 µg/g for all iron meteorites, and those in the IIAB-, IID- and IVB-bands with different SNRs.

5.4.2 The Effect of Low SNR

Perfect measurements are not achievable in practice. The data quality is described by the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the observation. Higher SNR requires either larger instruments, longer observation or both. Both size and exposure time scale as the square of the SNR demanded. This rapidly becomes infeasibly expensive. Hence it is useful to find the minimum SNR that can provide the information needed.

For all SNR=20,10,5, the IIAB- and IVB-bands promise ~3-fold increased likelihood of Pt-rich meteorites than random selection. With SNR=10, there is a twofold probability improvement. However, with a SNR of 20, the IID-band provides marginal improvements (4.3%) on random selection from a pool of all iron meteorites and SNR=10, only 16% of meteorites

in the IID-band are Pt-rich compared to 23% for random selection from all iron meteorites.

5.4.3 Total PGE abundance

I determined the total PGE abundance for the 119 iron meteorites for which the literature data were available. The range of total PGE values spans from 3.88 to 180.9 µg/g and has a mean value of 35.43 µg/g. This means without selecting for specific metallic asteroids we have a ~3-fold improvement on typical Earth mines. Applying Ni-band selection, as discussed in Section 5.4, is it possible to increase the probability of high-PGE. The distribution of total PGE abundance across iron meteorite groups is shown in Figure 5.6 and the mean total PGE is presented in Table 5.4. Group IVB has the highest

Figure 5.6 - Total PGE abundance (µg/g) of meteorites in each iron meteorite group. Blue diamonds represent individual meteorites.

average abundance with total PGE present at 130 $\mu\text{g/g}$, followed by IID at 54 $\mu\text{g/g}$ and IIAB at 48 $\mu\text{g/g}$.

Table 5.4 - Mean total PGE by iron meteorite group

Group	No. of Samples	Mean Total PGE($\mu\text{g/g}$)
IVB	9	129.7
IID	6	53.75
IIAB	15	48.28
IIC	3	45.49
ungr	4	43.63
IIE	4	32.44
IIIAB	16	26.89
IC	8	23.86
IIIF	5	23.24
IIIE	7	19.95
IAB	16	19.64
IIF	1	18.81
IVA	7	17.99
IIICD	5	16.35
IIG	1	3.88

5.4.4 Summary of Results

This section outlines how to evaluate an asteroid for mining according to the two metrics; confidence of high-Pt and total PGE. We do not discuss delta-v considerations and assume that all asteroids measured during the assay mission will be accessible for mining.

The first metric we consider is the confidence that a specific Ni measurement corresponds to a Pt-rich asteroid. If we are interested in how many meteorites within an Ni-band have $\text{Pt} > 20 \mu\text{g/g}$, then for $\text{SNR}=20$ the IVB-band is most promising with 83% of Pt-rich meteorites. The IIAB-band meteorites are a close

second at 72%. The IID-band meteorites reach only 27%, no better than choosing at random. At $\text{SNR}=5$ the IVB- and IIAB-bands drop to $\sim 40\%$, still about a two-fold improvement on random selection of any metallic meteorite. These findings are summarized in Figure 5.5.

If we instead look at the fraction of meteorites that fall into the group defining each Ni-band, then the IIAB-band has 100% of meteorites in the IIAB group for $\text{SNR}=20$ dropping to 56% for $\text{SNR}=5$.

The number of samples available for each group of meteorites (Table 5.2) must be considered when discussing confidence. Group IIAB has a total of 79 meteorites for which Pt data is available and 15 for which all PGE data is available. Group IID has just 18 meteorites and group IVB only 9. There are an additional 6 IVB group meteorites for which the Pt abundance has not been recorded, these measurements would increase the sample size usefully. We make the assumption that the available samples are representative of the parent body from which they are derived.

The second metric is the average total PGE in meteorites by group (Figure 5.6, Table 5.4). Our results in Section 5.4 identify the IVB group as the most PGE-rich, with more than a

twofold increase in PGE present in the IID and IIAB groups.

Caveats:

4. If all IIAB meteorites are from 1 body then we must treat it as only 1 sample with the average Pt abundance of all IIAB meteorites. With only 1 parent body for each meteorite groups the effective sample size is smaller.
5. We approximate that all PGEs are extracted in the same process and there isn't any major efficiency trade off between the extraction of particular PGEs over others.

5.5 Mission recommendations

Based on these three considerations, we make the following recommendations:

- ◆ An asteroid with Ni abundance 95-105 mg/g is not a good candidate for mining; even with perfect measurement, less than 50% of the meteorites within this Ni-band belong to the IID group and less than 30% have $Pt > 20 \mu\text{g/g}$.
- ◆ IVB is a promising mining candidate, with a total PGE average of 129.7 and $Pt > 20 \mu\text{g/g}$ present in all IVB meteorites. However, the meteorite sample size is small and would benefit from measurement of more IVB meteorites.

- ◆ The IIAB-band is the most promising candidate, with 79 meteorite samples and for $\text{SNR}=10$, greater than 50% of meteorites above $20 \mu\text{g/g}$ and 83% of meteorites in IIAB-band belonging to the IIAB group.

With a SNR of 10, there would be a twofold improvement in the probability of selecting a PGE-rich asteroid within the IIAB- and IVB-bands. A SNR of 5 would still be worthwhile for these Ni-bands. Ni abundance would have to be measured with proximate spectral analysis (Section 5.6).

5.6 Proximity assay methods

Given the above analysis, measuring the Ni content of an asteroid is likely to be a good indicator of its PGE content.

Very little is known about the composition of asteroids. The majority of asteroids have no spectral classification and are missing other important data attributes. Without full information it is impossible to fully estimate the true value of an asteroid or the cost of mining it. It would however be extremely time-consuming and expensive to visit hundreds of asteroids to collect samples. Thus, we need to

develop techniques that minimize the cost and time needed for surveying the precious metal content of asteroids.

Remote (telescopic) spectra can narrow the search to exclude stony asteroids and locate likely metallic ones. However, Ni content measurements are not possible remotely.

Stars produce radiation that is a near-perfect black body. This radiation passes through clouds of vaporized materials surrounding the stars, producing characteristic sharp absorption lines. We can determine the composition of stars by observing their absorption spectra.

Asteroids, however, are cold solid bodies and so their material produces only a few broad features. Hence the limited information obtained from telescopes. Proximity measurements from visiting spacecraft are needed.

There are 3 proximity methods that may be useful for analyzing the composition of asteroids while avoiding the complexities of contact operations: Laser Ablation, X-ray fluorescence and gamma-ray spectroscopy (GRS).

5.6.1 Laser Ablation

Remote (~10 km) composition analysis may be achieved by heating a distant target to the point of vaporization using a high-power laser.

This does two things: a black body is created on the surface of the asteroid and a cloud of vapor is ejected from the asteroid. Spectral analysis can then reveal elemental and molecular absorption lines in the blackbody spectrum as it passes through the cloud of ejecta (Hughes et al., 2015).

The energy required for this process is equal to the energy needed to bring the surface material to the melting point from its initial temperature plus the energy required to heat that material until it vaporizes. For most meteorite materials vaporization requires flux of ~10MW/m² (Hughes et al., 2015). Similar thermodynamic analyses can be done to produce a specific flux values for metallic asteroids where conduction will be more important and fewer compounds are present.

Hughes et al. (2015) discusses stand-off molecular composition analysis in which lasers deliver sufficient flux to vaporize distant targets. They have begun to develop systems that might achieve this goal. The CETAC LSX-200 laser ablation system has been developed to analyze trace elements with a sensitivity in the ppb range (Campbell and Humayan, 1999). This system has been applied to a set of iron meteorites in the lab to demonstrate the laser microprobe's analytical capability for the determination of platinum group

elements (PGEs) with a spatial resolution of $\sim 20 \mu\text{m}$, comparable to that of dynamic secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS).

■ Advantages:

- *ideal for application with metal asteroids which have high thermal conductivity and lower melting temperatures than silicates*
- *sub-surface measurement; resultant spectrum will not be affected by space weathering processes*

■ Issues:

- *requires large energy input*
- *point measurement may not reflect body average*

5.6.2 X-Ray Fluorescence

X-ray Fluorescence (XRF) observations of asteroids can reveal their true type, regardless of space weathering that can redden the optical and near-infrared spectra (Hong et al., 2016). XRF enables the measurement of spatial variation of both the absolute elemental abundances (Hong et al., 2016). The bulk composition of iron meteorites is dominated by Fe and Ni. Ni ranges between 4-25% wt, with Fe making up the rest. The emission lines for Fe ($\sim 6.4 \text{ keV}$) and Ni (~ 7.5

keV) are easily resolved with CCD detectors at $\Delta E \sim 100 \text{ eV}$ (Hong et al., 2016).

To estimate the orbital distance required to achieve a suitable SNR value we look to the NASA's Near Earth Asteroid Rendezvous (NEAR) Shoemaker mission (Cheng, 1997). NEAR carried an XRS with a spatial resolution of $\sim 3 \text{ km}$ at a distance of 40 km from the asteroid's surface (Nittler et al., 2001). Significant NEAR XRS data were acquired while the NEAR spacecraft was in 50 km and 35 km orbits around the center of mass of Eros (Nittler et al., 2001). During solar flares, statistically significant results were obtained in a relatively short period of time, while non-flaring periods required the co-addition of many more spectra to obtain significant results (Nittler et al., 2001).

■ Advantages:

- *high angular resolution ($< 1^\circ$)*
- *fairly wide field of view ($> 1^\circ$)*
- *extends to high energies ($0.3\text{-}15 \text{ keV}$) for detection of heavy elements*
- *whole body values*
- *penetrates to $\sim 20 \mu\text{g/g}$*
- *can begin during approach*

■ Issues:

- *best results at Solar max. (11 year cycle, last peak was 2013 (weak), next peak should be 2024)*
- *requires long exposures (few months) at each asteroid*
- *sunlit side only*

5.6.3 Gamma-ray Spectroscopy

GRS measures composition down to depths of tens of centimeters with very broad spatial resolution (Evans et al., 2001), making it suitable for analysis of asteroid bulk composition. For asteroid applications, GRS relies on cosmic rays incident on the metallic body to excite the atoms and emit gamma-rays.

At γ -ray wavelengths ($\lambda < 0.03$ nm), the Fe and Ni spectra are dominated by strong γ -ray with the energy 7.639 ± 0.004 MeV and 8.997 ± 0.005 MeV, respectively (Kinsey and Bartholomew, 1953).

A GRS was selected as one of the experiments onboard the the NEAR-Shoemaker mission based on its ability to determine spatially-resolved elemental composition of the target asteroid (Evans et al., 2001). A review of the NEAR-Shoemaker GRS by Evans et al. (2001) determined that the best data were collected on the surface of Eros after the

controlled descent. More analysis is required to determine whether a useful SNR (~ 10) can be achieved while in orbit and, if so, at what distance.

Cherepy et al. (2009) discuss The application of strontium iodide gamma-ray detectors for weak sources. They measure an energy resolution of 2.6-2.8% for 662 keV. Further development to achieve its limiting resolution for gamma ray spectroscopy of $\sim 2\%$ at 662 keV is underway.

■ Advantages:

- *measures composition to depths of 10s of cm*

■ Issues:

- *lower angular resolution than XRF*

5.7 Next Steps

This is by no means a complete assessment of the feasibility of mining asteroids for precious metals. There are a number of areas I would like to elaborate on. They are as follows:

- Measure PGE levels in a larger sample of iron meteorites.
- Perform a similar analysis with other precious metals including Au and REEs.

- Determine average total value of extractable metals per meteorite group, accounting for extraction efficiency tradeoffs for different metals.
- Explore the feasibility of measuring trace element abundances in Zodiacal Light.
- Perform spectral analysis and orbital determination for more NEAs, in particular those with $\Delta v < 6 \text{ km/s}$.
- Explore the requirements of an assay mission more thoroughly, determining which of the tools discussed in Section 5.6 are most suitable.
- Estimate the cost of an assay mission and the predicted increase in profit such an effort would bring.

6. Conclusions and Future Work

In this thesis I have explored planetary formation through the lens of Near-Earth Asteroids, meteorite minerals and iron meteorite trace element abundances.

Chapter 1 provided an overview of current theories in planet formation and classification systematics for asteroids and meteorites.

Chapter 2 presented 8 visible spectra of NEAs that had not been previously classified, in addition to 14 previously classified spectra for comparison. Following the process outlined in Bus and Binzel (2001), the breakdown of the 8 NEAs is: X S-type, Y C-type and Z X-type. As discussed in Galache et al. (2015), there is a need for rapid characterization of the NEA population. This work affirms that preliminary type-characterization can be performed with visible spectroscopy alone. Detailed steps and

the python script for spectral reduction and classification is available online at (www.cfa.harvard.edu).

Chapter 3 presented a database of 62 meteorite minerals. The distribution of meteorite minerals across different meteorite groups is plotted as a histogram and discussed. Of 62 meteorite minerals, 18 have been found on Earth following their discovery in meteorites and 19 have been synthesized, 3 of the minerals have been found on Earth and synthesized. 3 examples of interesting meteorite mineral properties are listed, encouraging further studies of these minerals which may have important industrial applications. Future studies may benefit greatly from dating the minerals. The intention of this database is to make meteorite mineral literature more tractable.

Chapter 4 presented a database of iron meteorite trace elemental abundances. The database contains 730 meteorites and provides the abundance of Ni, Ga, Ge, Co, Cu, Ir, Pt, Rh, Pd, Os, Re, Sb and W. The database is 30% complete. This database was compiled from 24 papers published between 1967 and 2003. This collection of data allows better exploration of relationships between elemental abundances in iron meteorites and within particular groups of iron meteorites. These relationships provide insight into the conditions in which the iron meteorites formed. This database would benefit from additional data. Evatt et al., (2016) discusses a potential reserve of iron meteorites 10-50cm under the surface of the Antarctic ice.

Chapter 5 presented an asteroid mining application of the iron meteorite trace element database. This statistical analysis discusses the probability of identifying a high-Pt (>20ppm) metallic asteroid based on measured Ni-abundance. Platinum group metals have been identified in iron meteorites at abundances of 10-20X that found in Earth mines. These high abundances make the parent asteroids of Pt-rich meteorites potentially profitable targets for mining. However, based on preliminary calculations, costs for a platinum group mining mission exceed the profit that would be made from sales of these metals at current market value. For this analysis we assume that the iron meteorite database is representative of the near-Earth asteroid population.

7. References

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8. Appendix

Table A2 - Glossary of Mineral Properties

Property	Description
Chemical formula	an expression which states the number and type of atoms present in a molecule of a substance
Type meteorite	meteorite in which the mineral was discovered
Publication	the journal article or conference proceeding discussing the discovery of the mineral
Crystal habit	a description of the shapes and aggregates that a certain mineral is likely to form
Occurrences	the other meteorites in which a particular meteorite mineral has been found
Crystal system	the classification given to the arrangement of atoms within the crystal
Hardness	a measure of the strength of the structure of the mineral relative to the strength of its chemical bonds
Density	a measure of the weight to volume ratio for a mineral
Cleavage	the splitting of a mineral along a flat, smooth plane
Fracture	a description of the way a mineral tends to break
Tenacity	describes the reaction of a mineral to stress such as crushing, bending, breaking, or tearing
Streak	the color of the mark a mineral makes when scratched on a white ceramic plate
Lustre	the manner in which a mineral reflects light
Diaphaneity	describes whether the mineral is transparent, translucent or opaque
Optics	used here to describe whether mineral has one or two optical axes (uniaxial or biaxial)
Refractive index	the ratio of the angle at which light enters and is bent as it enters a mineral
Pleochroism	the effect of showing different colors depending on the direction from which the mineral is observed
Birefringence	difference between the highest and lowest refractive index in a mineral
Extinction	the angle at which cross-polarized light dims, as viewed through a thin section of a mineral in a petrographic microscope
2V angle	the angle between the two optic axes of a biaxial mineral